

D6.13: Social Acceptance Studies Report

V.4 - November 2022

Status of deliverable: Public

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	Key Event	Completed
1	Draft version: Initial Review and Comment	23 November 2022
2	Submission of Final Deliverable	24 November 2022
3	Final Approval of Deliverable	30 November 2022

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Abbreviations

WWTP	Wastewater Treatment Plant
WTT	Water Treatment Technology

Section I. Introduction

The social acceptance research presented in this Deliverable (D6.13 Social Acceptance Studies) was designed to inform the implementation of the Project Ô water treatment innovations in four countries: Spain, Croatia, Italy, and Israel. Indeed, the data collection undertaken in each of these locations primarily focussed on attitudes toward the technology-based innovations for water treatment being implemented in respondents' local Project Ô demosite. Further background information was collected through these studies to identify factors affecting social acceptance in each demonstration site's region. The social acceptance research for the project was designed and implemented by the Institute for Methods Innovation, one of the Project Ô partners and the Work package 6 lead.

To measure these attitudes, an explainer video of Project Ô's implementation of innovative water treatment technologies focusing on the project's innovation work in the respondents' country was produced. The survey design used in these studies measured key aspects of local views about local Project Ô innovation plans for water reuse, circular water economy and related issues. To understand their background views relevant to water reuse, respondents were asked about their local water consumption patterns, their perceptions of the local water supply and their familiarity with water treatment technology. To understand differences in perceptions about environmental factors, respondents were asked to indicate their views related to different aspects of environmental attitudes relevant to water treatment innovations. This is important for clarifying drivers of social acceptance of new water treatment solutions. Finally, to understand the role of trust towards science and technology, scientists and engineers, and the European Commission in social acceptance of Project Ô's innovation work.

Section II. Methods

The social acceptance studies were conducted using social scientific tools and research methodology. The research was developed with the aim of enabling comparability between the four geographic locations where implementations are taking place in the project to evaluate the acceptability of the Project Ô water treatment technologies. This task involved the following:

- Developed methods and supporting methodological framework for survey-based research in each region where a Project Ô demosite is located.
- Implemented the collection and translation of social acceptance survey data in each of these regions.
- Developed and implemented an analysis and reporting framework for both site-specific and comparative analysis.

(a) Survey Methods

The design of the social acceptance research used primarily quantitative and supplementary qualitative elements. The research design ensured the standardisation and comparability of measurement of public assessments in each demonstration site's region. The data collection method used for the social acceptance research was a multilingual, mixed methods questionnaire.

Ethics was an integral part of the development and implementation of this task. It is pivotal to achieving research excellence and a necessity for the conduct of internationally recognised good practice in social research. Prior to the social acceptance studies beginning within WP6, IMI prepared documentation for compliance with the regulatory framework for protecting personal data specified in EU Directive 95/46/EC (e.g., procedures for data collection, storage, protection and processing) and applied for ethics approval. Ethics approval was sought and granted via the University of Aalborg, with the support of Professor Brady Wagoner. Ongoing reviews for General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) compliance and quality assurances were led by IMI's designated DPO (Dr Aaron M Jensen) and Operations Director (Lars

Lorenz), experts in data protection and associated legal and ethical requirements.

(b) Data collection

Data were collected with the support of a panel survey provider within each region. The sampling radius for recruitment of survey respondents started close to the demonstration site, and then was gradually expanded until reaching the target sample size of at least 200 respondents¹.

Extensive checks were performed on the data and all responses not passing these checks were excluded. This was conducted continuously throughout the data collection process until the target sample sizes were reached, only counting responses which passed screening. This quality assurance process was conducted by the Institute for Methods Innovation, with results shared with the panel survey provider.

The quality screening process targeted two dimensions on a per-response level. The first is “flatlining”, a pattern where respondents always pick the same response in a Likert-type question to complete the survey faster. A scoring system was developed to assess response quality and relevance to ensure that no problematic contributions are retained. This system assigned points on a scale from 0 (no flatlining) to 1 (all question blocks flatlined). These points were added to the second approach to assessing responses, which was by checking qualitative response items. The survey had a set of open-ended questions asking respondents to list words that came to mind after watching a video. Each word was manually checked based on the context relating to the survey or perceptions. Any word that did not align with the range of relevant topics was flagged accordingly. A scoring scheme of 0 (no irrelevant words) to 1 (all irrelevant words) was used to determine the ratio of irrelevant responses. In combination, both scoring schemes yielded a score from 0 to 2, where all responses scoring 1 or higher were excluded from the dataset due to questionable response quality and relevance. New participants were recruited

¹ Respondents were compensated for their participation through an established reward system operated by the survey panel provider, “TGM Research” (tgmresearch.com).

to replace excluded participants in order to maintain the target sample size for the region.

(c) Survey Analysis

Additional quality controls were employed to assess the presence of skewness in the data by gender, age, and education level. Cross-tabulations showing any systematic differences found in social acceptance of proposed water treatment and management innovations across these demographic variables above can be found in the first section of each case. Any systematic differences were considered for recommended actions that might increase social acceptance at the regional level for each of the demonstrator sites.

Section III. Spain Social Acceptance Case Study

3.01 Survey Sampling (Spain)

The sampling approach focused on the regions close to each demonstration site. This section sets out the demographic characteristics of the respondents to the survey in Spain, where recruitment centred on the area around Almendralejo (n=206 achieved sample).

(a) Gender

Respondents in the Spain survey self-reported their gender identification (Figure 1). There was a higher proportion of women (58%, n=119) than men (42%, n=87) in the sample. No respondents self-identified as non-binary.

Figure 1. Gender distribution of respondents (Spain)

(b) Age

The respondents' ages in the Spain survey were concentrated in the range between 19 and 48 (Figure 2). The age categories with the largest proportions were 19-28 years (37%, n=59), 29-38 years (31%, n=65), and 39-48 years (24%, n=50), followed by 49-58 years (10%, n=20). Whereas much smaller proportions were between the ages of 59-68 years (4%, n=9) and ≤ 18 years (2%, n=5). No respondents were identified in the ≥ 68 years category.

Figure 2. Age bands for survey respondents (Spain)

The mean age of respondents was 36, and the median was 35. This normal distribution indicates a skew toward younger and middle-aged respondents, particularly those between 18-48 in the Spain sample.

(c) Education

The distribution of educational qualifications of respondents in the Spain survey was slightly skewed towards those with less than a university degree (56%) compared to those with a university degree (44%) (Figure 3). Indeed, the educational qualification response category with the highest proportion was 'Below university degree' (54%, n=103). The response categories with the next highest proportion were 'University degree' (26%, n=49), followed by 'Postgraduate degree' (18%, n=35). The response category with the lowest representation was 'No educational qualification' (2%, n=4).

Figure 3. Educational qualifications of respondents (Spain)

(d) Relation to Water Treatment or Hydrology Fields

Respondents in Spain were asked about any prior employment (Figure 4) and knowledge of others employed (Figure 5) in water treatment or hydrology fields. Most respondents had no previous water industry/research-related employment (91%, n=187), and most did not personally know anyone employed (68%, n=141) in these related fields.

These results show that the sample in Spain did not have an excessive number of water-related research or industry participants. This helps give reassurance that this sample can provide a representative view of local perspectives on water reuse.

(e) Summary

The sampling approach focused on the local communities close to each demonstration site. The demographic characteristics of the respondents in Spain skewed toward men between the ages of 19-48 with education below university degree level. Before generalizing findings from the present study, these demographic and background differences must be considered.

3.02 Results from Social Acceptance (Spain)

This social acceptance survey was designed to inform the implementation of the Project Ô innovations across in Spain. Indeed, the survey's primary focus was on attitudes toward the technology-based innovations for water treatment being implemented in respondents' local Project Ô demosite. To measure these attitudes, an explainer video of Project Ô's implementation of innovative water treatment technologies focusing on the project's innovation work in the respondents' country was produced.

(a) Presentation of MOBILE3TECH water treatment technology

A pre-recorded presentation² of the local Project Ô circular water management solution, MOBILE3TECH, was presented to respondents in Spain, the region where it is being implemented (viz., Almendralejo, Spain). The video presentation provided a walk-through for participants, explaining water sustainability innovation solution being deployed in the respondents' local Project Ô's demosite. In particular, the case of Spain communicated the opportunity to increase water reuse with the MOBILE3TECH unit and how this benefits society, businesses, and the environment.

Figure 6. MOBILE3TECH module video stills (Spain)

The presentation introduced and contextualised the general problem of water treatment systems failing to work correctly when the pollutants in

² Available at [Project Ô | MOBILE3TECH Module](#)

wastewater become too concentrated, allowing unsafe water to go back to local rivers after treatment. The presentation explained how Project Ô technologies target and remove contaminants in wastewater before and after treatment at plants, protecting the environment and human health.

The final section provided more technical information about the MOBILE3TECH unit and the WTT implemented in the water treatment plant. Finally, the video concluded with an overview of the benefits of this technology module and how Project Ô innovations help to “close the loop” and ensure sustainable water use.

(b) Perceptions of Social Acceptance of Technology

After the presentation, respondents were asked to mark a point on a Likert-type scale between pairs of opposing adjectives (‘semantic differential’) to indicate attitudes towards the technology and degree of social acceptance.

(i) Perceived Utility of MOBILE3TECH Technology

Respondents in Spain generally had positive attitudes towards the utility of the MOBILE3TECH technology solution (Figure 7)³. Specifically, most respondents indicated that the technology module was Useful (78%, n=159) compared to those who viewed it as Useless (7%, n=15). A similarly large proportion of respondents indicated that the technology module was Valuable (75%, n=155) rather than Worthless (7%, n=17) and Essential (72%, n=149) rather than Unnecessary (9%, n=20). Finally, most respondents viewed the technology module as more Beneficial (73%, n=151) than Harmful (14%, n=30).

³ Useful-Useless (n=206, \bar{x} =1.83, SD=1.54)
 Valuable-Worthless (n=207, \bar{x} =1.75, SD=1.45)
 Essential-Unnecessary (n=206, \bar{x} =1.65, SD=1.60)
 Beneficial-Harmful (n=206, \bar{x} =1.54, SD=1.68)

Figure 7. Perceived Utility of MOBILE3TECH Technology Module (Spain)

These results show a broadly positive reception of the MOBILE3TECH solution from respondents in Spain. These results point to the primary areas where project efforts could reinforce social acceptance around the perceptions of utility, namely by focusing on the benefits and value of the Project Ô technology.

(ii) Perceived Reliability & Safety of MOBILE3TECH Technology

Respondents in Spain generally had positive attitudes towards the safety and reliability of the MOBILE3TECH technology module (Figure 8)⁴. Indeed, respondents indicated views of the technology module as Reliable (74%, n=152) rather than Unreliable (10%, n=21) and Safe (67%, n=137) compared to Risky (15%, n=31). However, compared to perceived utility, respondents were more undecided (as indicated by neutral responses) about the perceived reliability (n=33,16%) and safety (n=38,18%) of the MOBILE3TECH technology module.

Figure 8. Perceived Reliability & Safety of MOBILE3TECH Technology (Spain)

⁴ Safe-Risky (n=206, \bar{x} =1.29, SD=1.67)
 Reliable-Unreliable (n=206, \bar{x} =1.54, SD=1.61)

These results continue to show positive reception of the MOBILE3TECH solution from respondents in Spain. However, these results on social acceptance point to further project efforts that may bolster perceptions of the reliability and safety of the Project Ô technology.

(c) Qualitative data on social acceptance of Project Ô technology and solution implementation

This social acceptance survey research also included a qualitative, thought-listing dimension to clarify public views about the *technical* aspects of the Project Ô solution⁵. When expressing their views about the Project Ô water treatment technology being implemented at the local demosite, respondents in Croatia often mentioned descriptors such as ‘future’ ($n=17$), ‘new’ ($n=13$), ‘modern’ ($n=11$), and ‘innovative’ ($n=9$) were commonly given. These terms suggest that respondents view Project Ô technology in the form of the MOBILE3TECH module as cutting-edge. There were also lasting salient thoughts around Project Ô’s technology processes, such as ‘treatment’ ($n=9$) and ‘reuse’ ($n=8$).

Respondents expressed thoughts about the water treatment technology that shows how the ‘new’ and ‘treatment’ aspects are integrated differently. Some focused on the link between Project Ô technology and perceptions of human progress in a broad sense:

- *‘Future; Intelligence; Gets better; Evolution; Electric’* (Man, age 22)
- *‘Environment; Progress; Reuse; Future; Investments’* (Man, age 41)
- *‘Modern; Efficiency; New; Technology; World’* (Woman, 39)

Others focused more specifically on the practical benefits that modern or advanced technology development and use can bring:

- *‘Modern; Filtration; Security; Drinkable water; Water that can be drunk’* (Woman, 26)
- *‘Modern; More industries; More employment; Conscience; Aid’* (Man, age 33)

⁵ The survey question asked, ‘What comes to mind, if anything, when you think of the technology in the video you just watched?’ (referring to the video walk-through of the technology-based circular water economy solution introduced in the local demosite for the project.)

- *'Advance; Security; Future Saving; Recycling'* (Woman, age 36)

In terms of the responses that integrated Project Ô technology's 'treatment' function, there was an appreciation of the elements of the scientific process involved:

- *'Purify the water; Reutilization; Treatment; Purifiers; Chemistry'* (Man, 43)
- *'Detection of impurities; Agriculture; Detection; Treatment; Hydrography'* (Man, 38)

In addition, some responses indicated acknowledgment of the circularity of Project Ô technology, including explicitly positive associations with the 'reuse' of water:

- *'It is a good system to be able to reuse residual water; Excellent; Magnificent idea'* (Woman, 36)
- *'Wastewater; water reuse; Reuse residual water; Residual water restoration'* (Woman, 60)
- *'Take advantage of wastewater agriculture reuse; Wastewater treatment for new human use; Human reuse'* (Man, 40)

Overall, these qualitative responses indicate positive sentiment towards the technology, suggesting substantial social acceptance as presented by the project.

The survey also asked about public views on the overall solution and its implementation at the local demosite⁶. A prominent theme in these qualitative responses focused on a value-based judgment of it as 'good' ($n=18$). Digging deeper into the data, responses that included this favourable view also commonly included aspects of social or environmental benefits:

- *'That is very advanced; they take advantage of it; Good for the environment; Excellent; Well'* (Woman, 28)
- *'Healthy; Natural; Good; Modern'* (Man, 38)
- *'That technology is very important; My assessment of technology has changed; Big steps; Good for people and everything around us; Discovery'* (Woman, 38)

⁶ Respondents were given an opportunity to respond to the question 'What comes to mind, if anything, when you think about the video you just watched?' by typing up to 5 words in text boxes provided within the survey.

Respondents frequently focused specifically on the environmental benefits of implementing the technology-based solution at the local demosite:

- *'It is the best; You have to recycle the water; Sustainability guarantee'* (Man, age 42)
- *'Sewage treatment plant; Water; Project O; Environment; Pollution'* (Woman, age 27)
- *'Science at the service of nature; Quality; Health; Environment; Purification'* (Man, age 55)

Overall, respondents in Spain had similarly positive views about the technical aspects of the Project Ô solution and the overall implementation in the local demosite. These findings favour the social acceptance of technology-based circular water economy solutions in Spain.

3.03 Results from Factors Relevant to Social Acceptance (Spain)

The survey measured aspects of local views about local Project Ô innovation plans for water reuse, circular water economy, and related issues. Here, we report findings from each survey question before identifying key patterns relevant to Project Ô's innovative water treatment technologies.

(a) Background views relevant to water reuse

To understand their background views relevant to water reuse, respondents were asked about water consumption activities, their perceptions of the local water supply, and their familiarity with water treatment technology. These data help to shed light on factors that may affect social acceptance of water reuse innovations.

(i) Personal Water Consumption

Respondents in Spain were asked to mark a point between always and never to indicate their water consumption and which drinking water sources⁷ they used most often (Figure 9). Most respondents indicated their primary source of drinking water was most often (*always, usually, or frequently*) 'Water straight from the tap' (45%, n=93), compared to 'Filtered tap water' (19%, n=40) and 'Bottled water' (65%, n=135).

Figure 9. Water Sources for Personal Consumption (Spain)

⁷ Response options included three categories for 'Water straight from the tap' (n=208, \bar{x} =4.03, SD=2.28), 'Filtered tap water' (n=205, \bar{x} =2.59, SD=1.91), and 'Bottled water' (n=208, \bar{x} =5.17, SD=1.94)

Likewise, many respondents indicated irregular (*never* or *rarely*) personal use of 'Filtered tap water' (63%, n=130) and 'Bottled water' (12%, n=25), and 'Water straight from the tap' (37%, n=76). These results show the primary source of drinking water for respondents in Spain was straight from the tap. While a notable minority used bottled water with some regularity, it was not the predominant water source within this sample. This is an important implicit indicator of confidence in the local drinking water supply, based on behaviour.

(ii) Community Water Supply Perceptions

Respondents were asked to mark a point on a Likert-type scale between pairs of opposing adjectives ('semantic differential') to indicate attitudes towards the community water supply in Spain.

Respondents generally had positive attitudes towards the practical importance of local water supply (Figure 10)⁸. Indeed, most respondents indicated that the water supply was Essential (65%, n=136) compared to those who viewed it as Unnecessary (14%, n=30). A large proportion of respondents also indicated that the water supply was Valuable (64%, n=134) rather than Worthless (16%, n=34).

Figure 10. Perceived Utility of Community Water Supply (Spain)

Respondents in Spain generally had positive attitudes toward the safety and trustworthiness of the local water supply (Figure 11)⁹. Specifically, most respondents indicated that the water supply was Safe (54%, n=113) compared to those who viewed it as Risky (21%, n=43). A large proportion of respondents

⁸ Essential-Unnecessary (n=206, \bar{x} =1.49, SD=1.76)

Valuable-Worthless (n=208, \bar{x} =1.29, SD=1.76)

⁹ Safe-Risky (n=206, \bar{x} =0.94, SD=1.79)

Healthy-Unhealthy (n=207, \bar{x} =1.20, SD=1.61)

Trustworthy-Untrustworthy (n=207, \bar{x} =1.22, SD=1.69)

also indicated that the water supply was Healthy (65%, n=132) rather than Unhealthy (14%, n=30). Finally, most respondents viewed the water supply as more Trustworthy (65%, n=135) than Untrustworthy (14%, n=29).

Figure 11. Perceived Safety of Community Water Supply (Spain)

Respondents in Spain generally had positive attitudes towards the purity and naturalness of the water supply (Figure 12)¹⁰, albeit less positive than Croatia. Results show that most respondents indicated that the water supply was Natural (57%, n=117; versus 76% in Croatia) compared to those who viewed it as Unnatural (15%, n=32). A similarly large proportion of respondents indicated that the water supply was Clean (62%, n=130) rather than Dirty (18%, n=37) and Pure (63%, n=130; versus 77% in Croatia) rather than Impure (15%, n=31).

Figure 12. Perceived Cleanliness of Community Water Supply (Spain)

¹⁰ Nature-Unnatural (n=208, \bar{x} =1.00, SD=1.60)
 Clean-Dirty (n=208, \bar{x} =1.20, SD=1.72)
 Pure-Impure (n=206, \bar{x} =1.11, SD=1.56)

These results show respondents in Spain have broadly favourable views of community water supply as natural, clean, and pure. However, these results on social acceptance point to further project efforts that may bolster perceptions of how Project Ô technology can improve the community water supply.

(iii) Perceptions of Water Quality

To understand their background views relevant to water quality, respondents were asked about their perceptions of different categories¹¹ of local water supplies (Figure 13). Respondents indicated their views by marking a point on a Likert-type scale with anchors ranging from very good to very poor.

Most respondents in Spain view their water as good quality (very good or good). Indeed, the quality of drinking water (66%, n=136) was considered in the most favourable light compared to surface water¹² (47%, n=96) and ground water¹³ (53%, n=107) water sources. However, the 66% positive rating for drinking water, 47% positive for surface water and 53% positive for ground water in Spain is still much lower than for our respondents in Croatia, for example (positive ratings of 86% for drinking water, 70% for surface water and 63% for ground water in Croatia). Substantial levels of ‘neutral’ responses regarding surface and ground water suggest that fewer people have a clear sense of the quality of these water sources.

Figure 13. Water Quality Perceptions (Spain)

Respondents in Spain expressed positive views about water quality, particularly, the local drinking water. There is considerable uncertainty about surface and ground water supplies in Spain, which should be considered in

¹¹ Response options included three categories for ‘Drinking water’ (n=206, \bar{x} =3.83, SD=1.08), ‘Surface water’ (n=206, \bar{x} =3.26, SD=1.15), and ‘Ground water’ (n=202, \bar{x} =3.43, SD=1.11)

¹² Surface water was defined in the survey as including, ‘lakes, rivers, streams, creeks.’

¹³ Ground water was defined in the survey as ‘e.g., water that is drawn from aquifers or wells.’

future social acceptance communication initiatives. It may be beneficial to highlight the benefits of Project Ô circular water economy innovations for water quality in surface and ground sources in future public engagement.

(iv) Familiarity With Water Treatment Technology (WTT)

Respondents in Spain indicated their familiarity with water treatment technology (WTT) by marking a point on a Likert-type scale (Figure 14)¹⁴. Most respondents were familiar with this type of technology to some extent (slightly, somewhat, or moderately familiar; 71%, n=145). Much smaller proportions were either 'extremely' (10%, n=20) or 'not at all familiar' (19%, n=39) with this kind of technology.

Figure 14. Familiarity with water treatment technology (Spain)

These results show considerable recognition of WTT among Spain-based respondents, with a fairly small minority of them expressing complete unfamiliarity. This suggests there may be sufficient awareness of water treatment innovations in Spain to give a boost to initiatives aimed at garnering social acceptance of the project's solutions.

(b) Perceptions of the Environment

To understand differences in perceptions about environmental factors, respondents in Spain were asked to mark a point on a Likert-type scale with anchors for agree or disagree to indicate their views. Each of the statements related to different aspects of environmental attitudes relevant to water treatment innovations. This is important for clarifying drivers of social acceptance of new water treatment solutions in Spain.

¹⁴ Familiarity with WTT (n=204, \bar{x} =2.70, SD=1.23)

(i) Personal Perceptions of Relationship with the Environment

Respondents generally had positive perceptions of their relationship with the environment (Figure 15 and Figure 16)¹⁵. Most respondents agreed with the statement, ‘*My relationship to nature is an important part of who I am*’ (72%, n=148), with relatively few disagreeing (7%, n=16). Similarly, the majority agreed with the statement, ‘*The environment is important to me*’ (88%, n=184), and a much lower proportion disagreed (3%, n=6).

Figure 15. Personal Relationship with Environment (Spain)

These results were consistent for negatively framed attitude statements, where disagreement represents a positive relationship with the environment (Figure 16)¹⁶. Most respondents disagreed with the statement, ‘*There is nothing I can do personally to help protect the environment*’ (76%, n=158), with a low proportion who agreed (16%, n=34). Likewise, the majority disagreed with the statement, ‘*I never talk about the environment with my family*’ (62%, n=127). However, a much higher proportion agreed (21%, n=43) with this statement.

Figure 16. Personal Relationship with Environment (Reverse-coded) (Spain)

¹⁵ Relationship with Nature Identity (n=206, \bar{x} =5.35, SD=1.42)

Environment Importance (n=208, \bar{x} =5.98, SD=1.19)

¹⁶ Agency to Protect Environment (RC) (n=208, \bar{x} =2.55, SD=1.74)

Social Discuss Environment (RC) (n=207, \bar{x} =3.12, SD=1.77)

These results show broad recognition that the environment is important to respondents' self-perception. Results also offer a sense of self-efficacy regarding environmental protection. These are positive indicators for the project's communication efforts, suggesting that an environmental sustainability focus in social acceptance messaging may find a ready audience in Spain. However, results show that views about the environment within this pool of respondents are less commonly shared with others through discussion. This may point to additional framing options (e.g., economic benefits) in community engagement efforts.

(ii) General Perceptions of the Environment

Respondents also viewed protecting the environment as a priority (Figure 17)¹⁷. Most respondents agreed with the controversial statement, *'Keeping lakes and rivers clean is more important than protecting people's jobs'* (59%, n=121), with a lower proportion who disagreed (11%, n=24) and remained neutral (29%, n=60).

Figure 17. General Perceptions of Environment (Spain)

However, these results were less consistent with a negatively framed attitude statement (where disagreement represents prioritising the environment) that juxtaposes economic and environmental priorities (Figure 18)¹⁸. Specifically, while a plurality of respondents disagreed with the controversial statement, *'Protecting people's jobs is more important than the environment'* (37%, n=78), the proportions were still high for those who agreed (34%, n=70), and remained neutral (29%, n=59). No gender or age differences were evident in the patterns of responses to this level of agreement statement in Spain.

¹⁷ Importance of protecting jobs compared to rivers and lakes (n=205, \bar{x} =5.09, SD=1.57)

¹⁸ Importance of protecting jobs compared to environment (RC) (n=207, \bar{x} =3.96, SD=1.72)

Figure 18. General Perceptions of the Environment (Reverse-coded) (Spain)

Finally, respondents had mixed views about the capacity of modern science to resolve environmental issues (Figure 19)¹⁹. Similarly, results for those who disagreed with the controversial statement, ‘*Modern science will solve our environmental problems*’ (32%, n=65) were more equally divided between those who agreed (46%, n=96) and remained neutral (22%, n=45).

Figure 19. General Perceptions of the Environment (Reverse-coded) (Spain)

These results suggest that while the environment is an important part of how respondents perceive themselves, some respondents may be less inclined to prioritise environmental sustainability over important non-environmental factors. Thus, project communications should extend beyond environmental sustainability framing by also emphasising economic and other benefits associated with a shift to a circular economy model. This multi-faceted messaging approach may be effective at developing social acceptance in Spain, given the findings presented here.

¹⁹ Modern science capacity to resolve environmental issues (RC) (n=206, \bar{x} =4.31, SD=1.59)

(c) Trust in Science and the European Commission

To understand the role of trust towards science and technology, scientists and engineers, and the European Commission in social acceptance of Project Ô innovation work, respondents in Spain were asked to mark a point on a Likert-type scale with anchors for completely trust to completely distrust to indicate their views.

(i) Trust in Science & Technology

Respondents in Spain were asked about their trust in general towards science and technology (Figure 20)²⁰. Most respondents indicated high levels of trust (partial or complete) in 'science' (87%, n=146) and 'technology' (84%, n=173). These levels of trust are higher than what we found in Croatia, for example (Croatia: 72% trust in science and 67% trust in technology). There were only small differences between trust in science and trust in technology ($\pm 3\%$).

Figure 20. General Trust in Science & Technology (Spain)

Trust towards science and technology was overwhelmingly positive. A minority of respondents indicated some level of distrust (partial or complete) in both 'science' (2%, n=5) and 'technology' (5%, n=10), although completely distrust was exceedingly rare.

(ii) Trust in Scientists & Engineers

Respondents in Spain were asked about their levels of trust in specific categories of professionals relevant to Project Ô, namely scientists and

²⁰ Trust in Science (n=206, \bar{x} =1.36, SD=0.79)
Trust in Technology (n=206, \bar{x} =1.12, SD=1.02)

engineers (Figure 21)²¹. Most respondents indicated high levels of trust (partial or complete) in ‘scientists’ (81%, n=168) and ‘engineers’ (79%, n=163), with small differences between the two categories ($\pm 2\%$). These Spain results show particularly positive views about the trustworthiness of scientists and engineers, when compared to results from Croatia, for example (Croatia: Trust in ‘Scientists’ 65% and ‘Engineers’ 70%).

Figure 21. General Trust in Scientists & Engineers (Spain)

While these results show similarly high levels of trust for both scientists and engineers, it is worth noting there is some distrust in these professions amongst a minority of respondents (partial or complete) in both ‘scientists’ (5%, n=10) and ‘engineers’ (4%, n=10). It is also noteworthy that engineers gained a slightly higher level of trust compared to scientists.

(iii) Trust in The European Commission

Respondents in Spain were asked about their general level of trust in the European Commission (EC) (Figure 22)²². Respondents indicated mixed views, with a higher level of distrust (24%, n=50) compared to trust (38%, n=78) in the EC. This level of distrust among respondents in Spain is particularly, when compared, for example, to respondents in Croatia (Croatia: 40% Distrust in the EC and only 29% Trust). It is also noteworthy that a sizable proportion of respondents indicated neutral views (37%, n=76), which may indicate a lack of strong pre-existing perspectives on this topic.

²¹ Trust in Scientists (n=206, \bar{x} =1.16, SD=0.90)

Trust in Engineers (n=206, \bar{x} =1.07, SD=0.88)

²² Trust in European Commission (n=204, \bar{x} = 0.20, SD=1.07)

Figure 22. General Trust in European Commission (Spain)

This social acceptance survey extended questions about the EC to gather deeper, more project-relevant insights from respondents in Spain. This is important because the project is explicitly presented as an investment by the EC aimed at improving lives in Europe. Specifically, two additional questions were asked about the relationship between the EC and the respondents' local community (Figure 23 and Figure 24). For these questions, respondents were asked to mark a point on a Likert-type scale with anchors ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree to indicate their views.

Respondents had mixed levels of trust that EC actions would be appropriate (or aligned) for their community (Figure 23)²³. More respondents disagreed with the statement, '*I trust the European Commission to do what is right for my community*' (19%, n=39; versus) compared to those who agreed (39%, n=81) or indicated neutral (41%, n=68) views. Compared to respondents in Croatia, these results are more negative (19% disagree about trusting the EC in Spain versus 42% in Croatia; 39% agree in Spain versus 25% in Croatia).

Figure 23. Trust in EC - Align Actions for Community (Spain)

These results were consistent with the next question, which was a negatively framed attitude statement (where disagreement represents positive views) that juxtaposes EC and community support. Indeed, respondents in Spain had mixed levels of confidence about the ability of the EC to help their community (Figure 24)²⁴. Fewer respondents disagreed with the statement, '*I have very little confidence in the European Commission's ability to help my community*' (23%, n=46), compared to those who agreed (39%, n=81) or indicated neutral (38%, n=77) views.

²³ Trust that European Commission's Actions will be Appropriate for the Community (n=205, \bar{x} = 3.29, SD=1.02)

²⁴ Confidence in European Commission Ability to Help Community (n=204, \bar{x} = 3.21, SD=1.05)

Figure 24. Confidence in EC Ability to Help Community (Reverse-coded)
(Spain)

These results suggest that there is substantial distrust in the European Commission among respondents in Spain. This represents a major challenge to social acceptance of the project implementation and outcomes in Spain.

3.04 Discussion (Spain)

This social acceptance survey was designed to inform the implementation of the Project's innovations in Spain. The sampling approach focused on the local communities close to each demonstration site. The demographic characteristics of the respondents in Spain skew toward males between the ages of 19-48 with education below a university degree.

There was broad recognition of WTT among Spain-based respondents, with few expressing complete unfamiliarity. This base of existing awareness could be harnessed to bolster social acceptance initiatives in Spain. Respondents' experience with different types of local water consumption also clarifies the background position of respondents in Spain pertaining to social acceptance of water treatment. The primary source of drinking water for respondents in Spain was straight from the tap. While a notable minority used bottled water with some regularity, it was not the predominant water source within this sample. This was a noteworthy implicit marker of public confidence in local drinking water supplies. Indeed, this aligned with results that show generally positive views of water quality in Spain, with the strongest confidence in drinking water.

While the environment is an important part of how respondents in Spain perceive themselves, some respondents may be less inclined to prioritise environmental sustainability over important non-environmental factors. Furthermore, views about the environment within this pool of respondents were less commonly shared with others through discussion.

Respondents in Italy show levels of trust in the European Commission that were similar to Italy but higher than Croatia. One possible explanation could be perceptions of the EC as closer or more accessible to their community. Regardless, there was still evident distrust that may represent a challenge to social acceptance of the project implementation and outcomes in Spain because the project is explicitly presented as an EC investment aimed at improving lives in Europe.

Section IV. Croatia Social Acceptance Case Study

4.01 Survey Sampling (Croatia)

The sampling approach focused on the regions close to each demonstration site. This section sets out the demographic characteristics of the respondents to the survey that focused on the region around Omis, Croatia ($n=203$ achieved sample).

(a) Gender

Respondents in the Croatia survey self-reported their gender identification (Figure 25). There was a higher proportion of *men* (56%, $n=113$) compared to *women* (44%, $n=89$). No respondents self-identified as *non-binary*.

Figure 25. Gender distribution of respondents (Croatia)

(b) Age

The ages of respondents in the Croatia survey were concentrated at the younger age categories (Figure 26). The age bands with the largest proportions were *19-28 years* (37%, $n=66$), *29-38 years* (18%, $n=37$) and *39-48 years* (23%, $n=47$), followed by *49-58 years* (14%, $n=28$). Much smaller proportions were between the ages of *59-68 years* (3%, $n=7$), *≤18 years* (6%, $n=12$), and *≥68 years* (2%, $n=5$).

Figure 26. Age bands for survey respondents (Croatia)

The mean age of respondents was 36, and the median was 34. Overall, this age distribution indicates a skew towards younger and middle-aged respondents, particularly those between 18-48 in the Croatia sample.

(c) Education

The range of educational qualifications held by respondents in the Croatia sample had a little greater representation for those with less than a university degree (56%), compared to those with a university degree or more (45%) (Figure 27). Indeed, the educational qualification response category with the highest proportion was '*Below university degree*' (49%, $n=94$). The response categories with the next highest proportion were '*University degree*' (30%, $n=57$) followed by '*Postgraduate degree*' (15%, $n=28$). The response category with the lowest representation was '*No educational qualification*' (7%, $n=13$).

Figure 27. Educational qualifications of respondents (Croatia)

(d) Connections to Water Treatment Research or Industry

Respondents in Croatia were asked about any prior employment (Figure 4), and knowledge of others employed (Figure 5), in water treatment or hydrology fields. Most respondents had no prior water industry/research-related employment (93%, $n=187$) and most did not personally know anyone who was employed (71%, $n=142$) in these related fields.

These results show that the sample in Croatia did not have an excessive number of water-related research or industry participants. This helps give reassurance that this sample can provide a representative view of local perspectives on water reuse.

(e) Summary

The sampling approach focused on the local communities close to each demonstration site. The demographic profile of respondents in Croatia slightly over-represented men between the ages of 18-48 with an educational qualification below a university degree. These demographic and background differences must be considered before generalising findings from the present study.

4.02 Results from Social Acceptance (Croatia)

This social acceptance survey was designed to inform the implementation of the Project Ô innovations across Europe and in Croatia. Indeed, the primary focus of the survey was on attitudes towards the technology-based innovations for water treatment being implemented in respondents' local Project Ô demosite. To measure these attitudes, an explainer video of Project Ô's implementation of innovative water treatment technologies focusing on the project's innovation work in the respondents' country was produced.

(a) Presentation of Project Ô PHOTO.CAT solution

Respondents in Croatia were presented with a video recorded account²⁵ of the local Project Ô circular water economy solution, PHOTO.CAT, where it is being implemented (Omis, Croatia). The video presentation aimed to raise awareness of the water sustainability innovation solutions that are deployed in each of Project Ô's demosites. In this video recording, there are explanations of the role of the PHOTO.CAT unit in delivering water sustainability and why this is important.

Figure 30. PHOTO.CAT unit video stills (Croatia)

²⁵ Available at [Project Ô | PHOTO.CAT Unit](#)

In the video, the general problem of unsustainable industrial production and the need to reduce the environmental impact of water-intensive industries are discussed, in this case with a focus on clothing manufacturing. The presentation explained how Galeb, a clothing manufacturer in Croatia, is building its own water treatment plant using Project Ô technologies to purify and reuse water after the process of dyeing clothes.

The final section provided more technical information about the PHOTO.CAT unit, the WTT implemented in the water treatment plant. Finally, the video presentation concluded with an overview of the benefits of this technology and how Project Ô innovations help to “close the loop” and ensure sustainable water use.

(b) Results of Social Acceptance of Technology

After the presentation, respondents were asked to mark a point on a Likert-type scale between pairs of opposing adjectives (‘semantic differential’) to indicate attitudes towards the technology and degree of social acceptance.

(i) Perceived Utility of PHOTO.CAT Technology

The overwhelming majority of respondents in Croatia held generally positive attitudes towards the utility of PHOTO.CAT technology solution (Figure 31)²⁶. Specifically, most respondents indicated that the technology module was *Useful* (79%, $n=160$) compared to those who viewed it as *Useless* (10%, $n=21$). A similarly large proportion of respondents indicated that the technology module was *Valuable* (73%, $n=147$) rather than *Worthless* (12%, $n=25$), and *Essential* (74%, $n=152$) rather than *Unnecessary* (11%, $n=23$). Finally, most respondents viewed the technology module as more *Beneficial* (71%, $n=144$) than *Harmful* (15%, $n=32$).

²⁶ Useful-Useless ($n=203$, $\bar{x}=1.73$, $SD=1.54$)
Valuable-Worthless ($n=201$, $\bar{x}=1.52$, $SD=1.66$)
Essential-Unnecessary ($n=203$, $\bar{x}=1.70$, $SD=1.55$)
Beneficial-Harmful ($n=202$, $\bar{x}=1.44$, $SD=1.76$)

Figure 31. Perceived Utility of PHOTO.CAT Module (Croatia)

The survey results in Croatia show strongly positive views about the PHOTO.CAT solution. Also visible in the results are points where project communication efforts could reinforce social acceptance, especially relating to perceptions of utility, namely the benefits and value of the PHOTO.CAT water treatment module.

(ii) Perceived Reliability & Safety of PHOTO.CAT Technology

Most respondents in Croatia expressed positive attitudes about the safety and reliability of the PHOTO.CAT technology module (Figure 32)²⁷. Indeed, respondents indicated views of the PHOTO.CAT module as *Reliable* (64%, $n=128$) rather than *Unreliable* (17%, $n=35$), and *Safe* (60%, $n=121$) compared to *Risky* (21%, $n=43$). However, compared to perceived utility, respondents were more undecided (as indicated by neutral responses) about the perceived reliability ($n=39, 19%$) and safety ($n=38, 19%$) of the PHOTO.CAT technology module.

²⁷ Safe-Risky ($n=202, \bar{x}=0.87, SD=1.77$)

Reliable-Unreliable ($n=202, \bar{x}=1.09, SD=1.65$)

Figure 32. Perceived Reliability & Safety of the PHOTO.CAT Water Treatment Module (Croatia)

The picture emerging from these findings is of a positive reception of the PHOTO.CAT solution from respondents in Croatia. The main area to target for future social acceptance initiatives would be perceptions of the reliability and safety of the PHOTO.CAT module, based on these findings.

(iii) Qualitative results on social acceptance of Project Ô technology and solution implementation

This social acceptance survey research also included a qualitative, thought-listing dimension aimed at clarifying public views about the technical aspects of the Project Ô solution being implemented in Croatia²⁸. When describing the Project Ô water treatment technology called PHOTO.CAT being implemented at the local demosite, respondents in Croatia often mentioned descriptors such as ‘modern’ ($n=14$), ‘advanced’ ($n=13$), ‘future’ ($n=11$) and ‘innovative’ ($n=8$). These terms suggest that respondents viewed this Project Ô water treatment solution as cutting-edge. The PHOTO.CAT module was also viewed as ‘useful’ ($n=9$) in delivering water ‘purification’ ($n=9$).

Respondents’ thoughts about the PHOTO.CAT water treatment technology being implemented in Croatia shows how the ‘modern’ and ‘useful’ aspects are integrated in different ways. Some focused on the links between modern technology, innovation and environmental conservation (or restoration).

- *‘New; Innovation; Modern; Conservation of nature’* (Woman, age 47)
- *‘Modern; Necessary; Future; Clean; Restored’* (Man, age 69)
- *‘Modern; Technology; Purification; Recycling’* (Man, age 42)

Respondents also gave value-based judgments such as ‘good’ ($n=9$) and ‘excellent’ ($n=8$), when asked about the Project Ô water treatment technology.

²⁸ The survey question asked, ‘What comes to mind, if anything, when you think of the technology in the video you just watched?’ (referring to the video walk-through of the technology-based circular water economy solution introduced in the local demosite for the project.)

- *'Inspiring; Smart'* (Woman, age 24)
- *'Excellent technology; Super; Interesting; Fantastic'* (Man, age 21)

Moreover, these qualitative data showed respondents anticipating the value of continuing to scale up this kind of technology (emphases added below).

- *'Innovative; Usable; There should be more industries that use water like that; More environmentally friendly'* (Woman, age 35)
- *'Useful technology; Gives hope; Mandatory to apply; Water protection in the future; A better world'* (Woman, age 48)

These qualitative responses indicate positive sentiment towards the technology, suggesting substantial social acceptance of the technology as it is currently presented by the project.

The survey also asked about public views on the overall solution and its implementation at the local demosite²⁹. The prominent themes in these qualitative responses focused on Project Ô 'technology' ($n=19$). Digging deeper into the data, it is possible to delineate the ways in which different respondents thought about 'technology' within the Project Ô implementation in Croatia.

Some respondents' thoughts around the technological approach of Project Ô implementation were linked to its environmental and ecological purpose.

- *'Care for the environment; The power of technology'* (Woman, age 30)
- *'Water reuse; Clean water; Technology; Ecology; Environment'* (Man, age 49)
- *'Innovation; Ecology; Technology'* (Woman, age 32)

Other respondents' views about the Project Ô implementation at the demosite were linked to broader notions of optimism about the importance of technological solutions generally.

- *'Technology should be used more'* (Man, 23)
- *'Excellent project; They should invest in that technology'* (Woman, 48)

²⁹ Respondents were given an opportunity to respond to the question 'What comes to mind, if anything, when you think about the video you just watched?' by typing up to 5 words in text boxes provided within the survey.

- *'Technology; Solutions'* (Woman, 39)

In addition, some responses were focused on Project Ô technology's specific technical purpose within the demosite in terms of purification.

- *'Water; Technology; Improvement; Cotton T-shirts; Purification'* (Woman, 22)
- *'Water; Purification; Technology; Resources; Industry'* (Man, 48)

Respondents also frequently emphasised the environmental benefits of implementing the technology-based solution at the local demosite, noting key concepts such as 'clean' ($n=12$), 'life' ($n=11$), 'environment' ($n=11$), 'nature' ($n=10$), and 'ecology' ($n=9$).

Some respondents focused on the outcome of the purification technology on water itself.

- *'Clean water; Renewed; Without chemicals'* (Man, 69)
- *'Saving water in industry; Clean the environment'* (Woman, 48)
- *'Cleaner water; Nicer environment; Help'* (Man, 22)

Other respondents focused more on potential benefits of the Project Ô implementation for nature.

- *'Nature preservation; Ecology'* (Woman, 22)
- *'Excellent; Smart; Worth the money; Savings; Nature'* (Man, 53)

Respondents also highlighted the human-centred benefits that Project Ô implementation could provide in terms of protecting a resource core to human survival.

- *'Water protection means human survival; Water is the source of life; Protect water at all costs; Man cannot live without water; Life with water'* (Man, 40)
- *'Necessary water for life; Polluted water; Improvement'* (Woman, 34)
- *'Without water there is no life'* (Woman, 58)

Ultimately, respondents in Croatia had similarly positive views about the technology aspects of the Project Ô solution and the overall implementation in the

local demosite. These findings bode well for social acceptance of technology-based circular water economy solutions in Croatia.

4.03 Results from Factors Relevant to Social Acceptance (Croatia)

The survey measured key aspects of local views about local Project Ô innovation plans for water reuse, circular water economy and related issues. Here, we report findings from each survey question before identifying key patterns relevant to Project Ô's innovative water treatment technologies.

(a) Background views relevant to water reuse

To understand their background views relevant to water reuse, respondents were asked about their water consumption behaviours, their perceptions of the local water supply and their familiarity with water treatment technology. These data help to shed light on factors that may affect social acceptance of water reuse innovations.

(i) Personal Water Consumption

Respondents in Croatia were asked to mark a point between *always* or *never* to indicate their personal water consumption and which drinking water sources³⁰ they used most often (Figure 33). Most respondents indicated their main source of drinking water was most often (*always, usually or frequently*) 'Water straight from the tap' (88%, $n=174$), compared to 'Filtered tap water' (25%, $n=49$) and 'Bottled water' (23%, $n=44$).

³⁰ Response options included three categories for 'Water straight from the tap' ($n=199$, $\bar{x}=6.05$, $SD=1.43$), 'Filtered tap water' ($n=197$, $\bar{x}=2.88$, $SD=2.04$), and 'Bottled water' ($n=199$, $\bar{x}=3.34$, $SD=1.49$).

Figure 33. Water Sources for Personal Consumption (Croatia)

Likewise, many respondents indicated irregular (*never or rarely*) personal use of 'Filtered tap water' (55%, $n=108$) and 'Bottled water' (36%, $n=71$), and 'Water straight from the tap' (6%, $n=10$). These results show the primary source of drinking water for respondents in Croatia was straight from the tap. While bottled water was used by a notable minority with some regularity, it was clearly not the predominant water source within this sample. This is a noteworthy behavioural indicator of confidence in the local supply of drinking water.

(ii) Community Water Supply Perceptions

Respondents were asked to mark a point on a Likert-type scale between pairs of opposing adjectives ('semantic differential') to indicate attitudes towards the community water supply in Croatia.

Respondents had generally positive attitudes towards the practical importance of local water supply (Figure 34)³¹. Indeed, most respondents indicated that the water supply was *Essential* (77%, $n=155$) compared to those who viewed it as *Unnecessary* (12%, $n=23$). A large proportion of respondents also indicated that the water supply was *Valuable* (75%, $n=152$) rather than *Worthless* (12%, $n=25$).

Figure 34. Perceived Utility of Community Water Supply (Croatia)

Respondents in Croatia had generally positive attitudes towards the safety and trustworthiness of the local water supply (Figure 35)³². Specifically, most

³¹ Essential-Unnecessary ($n=200$, $\bar{x}=1.81$, $SD=1.74$)

Valuable-Worthless ($n=201$, $\bar{x}=1.68$, $SD=1.67$)

³² Safe-Risky ($n=202$, $\bar{x}=1.34$, $SD=1.70$)

Healthy-Unhealthy ($n=201$, $\bar{x}=1.44$, $SD=1.59$)

respondents indicated that the water supply was *Safe* (68%, $n=138$) compared to those who viewed it as *Risky* (16%, $n=34$). A large proportion of respondents also indicated that the water supply was *Healthy* (72%, $n=145$) rather than *Unhealthy* (13%, $n=28$). Finally, most respondents viewed the water supply as more *Trustworthy* (64%, $n=130$) than *Untrustworthy* (19%, $n=39$).

Figure 35. Perceived Safety of Community Water Supply (Croatia)

Respondents in Croatia had generally positive attitudes towards the purity and naturalness of the water supply (Figure 36)³³. Results show that most respondents indicated that the water supply was *Natural* (76%, $n=154$) compared to those who viewed it as *Unnatural* (11%, $n=23$). A similarly large proportion of respondents indicated that the water supply was *Clean* (71%, $n=144$) rather than *Dirty* (17%, $n=35$), and *Pure* (77%, $n=156$) rather than *Impure* (11%, $n=23$).

Figure 36. Perceived Cleanliness of Community Water Supply (Croatia)

Trustworthy-Untrustworthy ($n=201$, $\bar{x}=1.18$, $SD=1.75$)
³³ Nature-Unnatural ($n=201$, $\bar{x}=1.72$, $SD=1.54$)
 Clean-Dirty ($n=203$, $\bar{x}=1.38$, $SD=1.77$)
 Pure-Impure ($n=201$, $\bar{x}=1.59$, $SD=1.63$)

These results show most respondents in Croatia have positive views of their community water supply as natural, clean, and pure. However, these results on social acceptance point to further project efforts that may bolster perceptions of how Project Ô technology modules can improve local water supplies through introducing circular water management.

(iii) Perceptions of Water Quality

To understand their background views relevant to water quality, respondents were asked about their perceptions of different categories³⁴ of local water supplies (Figure 37). Respondents indicated their views by marking a point on a Likert-type scale with anchors ranging from *very good* to *very poor*.

Most respondents in Croatia view their water as good quality (*very good* or *good*). Indeed, the quality of drinking water (86%, $n=174$) was viewed in the most positive light compared to surface water³⁵ (70%, $n=49$) and ground water³⁶ (63%, $n=44$) water sources. Substantial levels of ‘neutral’ responses regarding surface and ground water suggest that fewer people have a clear sense of the quality of these water sources.

Figure 37. Water Quality Perceptions (Croatia)

The social acceptance research shows positive views of water quality in Croatia, especially regarding the drinking water. There is considerable uncertainty about the status of surface and ground water supplies in Croatia, which should be considered in future social acceptance communication initiatives. It may be

³⁴ Response options included three categories for ‘Drinking water’ ($n=203$, $\bar{x}=4.22$, $SD=0.81$), ‘Surface water’ ($n=200$, $\bar{x}=3.86$, $SD=0.95$), and ‘Ground water’ ($n=194$, $\bar{x}=3.68$, $SD=0.99$).

³⁵ Surface water was defined in the survey as including, ‘lakes, rivers, streams, creeks’.

³⁶ Ground water was defined in the survey as ‘e.g., water that is drawn from aquifers or wells’.

beneficial to highlight the benefits of Project Ô circular water economy innovations for water quality in surface and ground sources in future public engagement.

(iv) Familiarity with Water Treatment Technology (WTT)

Respondents in Croatia indicated their level of familiarity with water treatment technology (WTT) by marking a point on a Likert-type scale (Figure 38)³⁷. Most respondents were familiar with this type of technology to some extent (*slightly, somewhat or moderately* familiar; 84%, $n=185$). Much smaller proportions were either extremely (6%, $n=13$) or not at all familiar (15%, $n=31$) with this kind of technology.

Figure 38. Familiarity with water treatment technology (Croatia)

These results show widespread familiarity with WTT among Croatia-based respondents, with relatively few expressing complete unfamiliarity. This is a promising finding, signalling a good starting position for social acceptance initiatives in Croatia relating to water treatment innovations.

(b) Perceptions of the Environment

To understand differences in perceptions about environmental factors, respondents in Croatia were asked to mark a point on a Likert-type scale with anchors for agree or disagree to indicate their views. Each of the statements related to different aspects of environmental attitudes relevant to water treatment innovations. This is important for clarifying drivers of social acceptance of new water treatment solutions in Croatia.

³⁷ Familiarity with WTT ($n=201$, $\bar{x}=2.71$, $SD=1.16$)

(i) Personal Perceptions of Relationship with Environment

Respondents had generally positive perceptions of their relationship with the environment (Figure 39 and Figure 40)³⁸. Most respondents agreed with the statement, *'My relationship to nature is an important part of who I am'* (77%, $n=156$), with relatively few disagreeing (14%, $n=29$). Similarly, the majority agreed with the statement, *'The environment is important to me'* (84%, $n=171$), and a much lower proportion disagreed (13%, $n=26$).

Figure 39. Personal Relationship with Environment (Croatia)

These results were consistent for negatively framed attitude statements, where disagreement represents a positive relationship with the environment (Figure 40)³⁹. Most respondents disagreed with the statement, *'There is nothing I can do personally to help protect the environment'* (80%, $n=163$), with a low proportion who agreed (13%, $n=27$). Likewise, the majority disagreed with the statement, *'I never talk about the environment with my family'* (67%, $n=134$). However, a much higher proportion agreed (33%, $n=48$) with this statement.

³⁸ Relationship with Nature Identity ($n=202$, $\bar{x}=5.28$, $SD=1.70$)
 Environment Importance ($n=202$, $\bar{x}=5.63$, $SD=1.70$)

³⁹ Agency to Protect Environment (RC) ($n=202$, $\bar{x}=2.58$, $SD=1.8$)
 Social Discuss Environment (RC) ($n=202$, $\bar{x}=3.18$, $SD=1.69$)

Figure 40. Personal Relationship with Environment (Reverse-coded) (Croatia)

These results show broad recognition that the environment is an important part of respondents' self-perception. Results also show a sense of self-efficacy regarding environmental protection. These are positive indicators for the project's communication efforts, suggesting that an environmental sustainability focus in social acceptance messaging may find a ready audience in Croatia. However, results show that positive views about the environment within this pool of respondents are less commonly shared with others through discussion. This may point to the need for other additional framing options (e.g., economic benefits) in community engagement efforts.

(ii) General Perceptions of the Environment

Respondents viewed protecting the environment as a priority (Figure 41)⁴⁰. Most respondents agreed with the controversial statement, '*Keeping lakes and rivers clean is more important than protecting people's jobs*' (56%, $n=112$), with a lower proportion who disagreed (22%, $n=45$) and remained neutral (22%, $n=57$).

Figure 41. General Perceptions of Environment (Croatia)

However, these results were less consistent with a negatively framed attitude statement (disagreement represents prioritising the environment) that compare economic and environmental priorities (Figure 42)⁴¹. Specifically, while a larger proportion of respondents disagreed with the controversial statement, '*Protecting people's jobs is more important than the environment*' (43%, $n=85$), proportions were high for those who agreed (30%, $n=58$) and remained neutral (29%, $n=57$).

⁴⁰ Importance of protecting jobs compared to rivers and lakes ($n=200$, $\bar{x}=4.76$, $SD=1.65$)

⁴¹ Importance of protecting jobs compared to environment (RC) ($n=200$, $\bar{x}=3.73$, $SD=1.52$)

Figure 42. General Perceptions of the Environment (Reverse-coded) (Croatia)

Finally, respondents had mixed views about the capacity of modern science to resolve environmental issues (Figure 43)⁴². Similarly, results for those who disagreed with the controversial statement, 'Modern science will solve our environmental problems' (43%, $n=109$) were more equally divided between those who agreed (36%, $n=73$) and remained neutral (29%, $n=57$).

Figure 43. General Perceptions of the Environment (Reverse-coded) (Croatia)

These results suggests that while the environment is an important part of how respondents perceive themselves, some respondents may be less inclined to prioritise environmental sustainability over important non-environmental factors. Thus, project communications should extend beyond environmental sustainability framing by also emphasising economic and other benefits associated with a shift to a circular economy model. This multi-faceted messaging approach may be effective at developing social acceptance in Croatia, given the findings presented.

⁴² Modern science capacity to resolve environmental issues (RC) ($n=202$, $\bar{x}=3.75$, $SD=1.59$)

(c) Trust in Science and the European Commission

To understand the role of trust towards science and technology, scientists and engineers and the European Commission in social acceptance of Project Ô innovation work, respondents in Croatia were asked to mark a point on a Likert-type scale with anchors for *completely trust* to *completely distrust* to indicate their views.

(i) Trust in Science & Technology

Respondents in Croatia were asked about trust towards science and technology (Figure 44)⁴³. Most respondents indicated high levels of trust (*partial* or *complete*) in 'science' (72%, $n=146$) and 'technology' (67%, $n=132$). There were only small differences between trust in science and trust in technology ($\pm 5\%$).

Figure 44. General Trust in Science & Technology (Croatia)

Trust towards science and technology was overwhelmingly positive. A minority of respondents indicated some level of distrust (*partial* or *complete*) in both 'science' (10%, $n=21$) and 'technology' (13%, $n=27$), although *completely distrust* was exceedingly rare.

(ii) Trust in Scientists & Engineers

Respondents in Croatia were asked about their levels of trust in specific categories of professionals relevant to Project Ô, namely scientists and engineers (Figure 45)⁴⁴. Most respondents indicated high levels of trust (*partial* or *complete*)

⁴³ Trust in Science ($n=201$, $\bar{x}=0.85$, $SD=1.04$)
Trust in Technology ($n=202$, $\bar{x}=0.73$, $SD=1.02$)
⁴⁴ Trust in Scientists ($n=201$, $\bar{x}=0.65$, $SD=1.07$)

in 'scientists' (65%, $n=132$) and 'engineers' (70%, $n=139$), with small differences between the two categories ($\pm 5\%$).

Figure 45. General Trust in Scientists & Engineers (Croatia)

While these results show similarly high levels of trust for both scientists and engineers, it is worth noting there is some distrust in these professions amongst a minority of respondents (*partial* or *complete*) in both 'scientists' (14%, $n=30$) and 'engineers' (12%, $n=23$). It is also noteworthy that engineers gained a slightly higher level of trust compared to scientists.

(iii) Trust in The European Commission

Respondents in Croatia were asked about their general level of trust in the European Commission (EC) (Figure 46)⁴⁵. Respondents indicated mixed views, with a higher level of distrust (40%, $n=80$) compared to trust (29%, $n=56$) in the EC. It is also noteworthy that a sizable proportion of respondents who indicated neutral views (32%, $n=63$), which may indicate a lack of strong pre-existing perspectives on this topic.

Figure 46. General Trust in European Commission (Croatia)

This social acceptance survey extended questions about the EC to gather deeper, more project relevant insights from respondents in Croatia. This is

Trust in Engineers ($n=200$, $\bar{x}=0.75$, $SD=0.95$)

⁴⁵ Trust in European Commission ($n=199$, $\bar{x}= -0.22$, $SD=1.12$)

important because the project is explicitly presented as an investment by the EC aimed at improving lives in Europe. Specifically, two additional questions were asked about the relationship between the EC and the respondents' local community (Figure 47 and Figure 48). For these questions, respondents were asked to mark a point on a Likert-type scale with anchors ranging from *strongly agree* to *strongly disagree* to indicate their views.

Respondents had mixed levels of trust that EC actions would be appropriate (or aligned) for their community (Figure 47)⁴⁶. More respondents disagreed with the statement, '*I trust the European Commission to do what is right for my community*' (42%, $n=83$) compared to those who agreed (25%, $n=49$) or indicated neutral (32%, $n=63$) views.

Figure 47. Trust in EC - Align Actions for Community (Croatia)

These results were consistent with the next question, which was a negatively framed attitude statement (where disagreement represents positive views) that juxtaposes EC and community support. Indeed, respondents had mixed levels of confidence about the ability of the EC to help their community (Figure 48)⁴⁷. Fewer respondents disagreed with the statement, '*I have very little confidence in the European Commission's ability to help my community*' (28%, $n=54$), compared to those who agreed (43%, $n=84$) or indicated neutral (31%, $n=62$) views.

Figure 48. Confidence in EC Ability to Help Community (Reverse-coded) (Croatia)

These results suggest that there is substantial distrust in the European Commission among respondents in Croatia. This represents a major challenge to

⁴⁶ Trust in European Commission Actions Appropriate for Community ($n=200$, $\bar{x}= 2.73$, $SD=1.04$)

⁴⁷ Confidence in European Commission Ability to Help Community ($n=200$, $\bar{x}= 3.20$, $SD=1.09$)

social acceptance of the project implementation and outcomes in Croatia.

4.04 Discussion (Croatia)

This social acceptance survey was designed to inform the implementation of the Project Ó innovations in Croatia. The sampling approach focused on the local communities close to each demonstration site. The distribution of demographic characteristics for respondents in Croatia leaned toward 19–48-year-old men with an education level below a university degree. This helps to clarify the representativeness of the sample for understanding local perspectives on water reuse and technology-based circular water management solutions.

There was broad recognition of WTT among Croatia-based respondents, with a relatively small minority expressing complete unfamiliarity. This suggests that the project may have a reservoir of awareness of water treatment innovations to draw upon when seeking social acceptance in Croatia. Respondents' water consumption behaviour further clarifies background factors affecting social acceptance of water reuse innovations. The primary source of drinking water for respondents in Croatia was straight from the tap. While a notable minority used bottled water with some regularity, it was not the predominant water source within this sample. This important behavioural indicator of confidence in the local drinking water supply aligns with the positive views of water quality (especially drinking water) that were expressed by respondents in Croatia.

While the environment is an important part of how respondents in Croatia perceive themselves, some respondents may be less inclined to prioritise environmental sustainability over important non-environmental factors. Furthermore, views about the environment were less commonly shared with others through discussion.

Respondents in Croatia had substantially lower trust in the European Commission (EC) than we found in Spain and Italy. The results suggest the possible explanation for why this trust faltered for respondents in Croatia: Perceptions of the EC as distant or inaccessible from their community. This may represent a challenge to social acceptance of the project implementation and

outcomes in Croatia because the project is explicitly presented as an EC investment aimed at improving lives in Europe.

Section V. Italy Social Acceptance Case Study

5.01 Survey Sampling (Italy)

The sampling approach focused on the regions close to each demonstration site. This section sets out the demographic characteristics of the respondents to the survey in Italy that focused on the region around Puglia (n=203 achieved sample).

(a) Gender

Respondents in the Italy survey self-reported their gender identification (Figure 49). There was an equal proportion of men (50%, n=105) compared to women (50%, n=104). No respondents self-identified as non-binary.

Figure 49. Gender distribution of respondents (Italy)

(b) Age Profile

Respondents in the Italy survey included substantial representation from age 19 through 68 (Figure 50). The age categories with the largest proportions were 19-28 years (24%, n=49), 29-38 years (19%, n=39) and 39-48 years (16%, n=33), followed by 49-58 years (18%, n=38). Whereas, much smaller proportions were between the ages of 59-68 years (14%, n=29), ≤18 years (4%, n=8), and ≥68 years (6%, n=12).

Figure 50. Age bands for survey respondents (Italy)

The mean age of respondents was 42, and the median was 40. Overall, this shows an approximately equal distribution for those between 18-58, with only a modest skew towards younger and middle-aged respondents in the Italy sample.

(c) Education

The distribution of educational qualifications of respondents in the Italy survey was strongly skewed towards those with less than a university degree level qualification (69% below vs. 31% above university degree level) (Figure 51). Indeed, the educational qualification response category with the greatest representation was 'Below university degree' (66%, n=125). The response categories with the next highest proportion were 'Postgraduate degree' (19%, n=36) followed by 'University degree' (12%, n=23). The response category with the lowest representation was 'No educational qualification' (3%, n=5).

Figure 51. Educational qualifications of respondents (Italy)

(d) Connections to Water Treatment Research or Industry

Respondents in Italy were asked about any prior employment (Figure 52), and knowledge of others employed (Figure 53), in water treatment or hydrology fields. Most respondents had no prior water industry/research-related employment (91%, n=190) and most did not personally know anyone who was employed (73%, n=153) in these related fields.

These results show that the sample in Italy did not have an excessive number of water-related research or industry participants. This helps give reassurance that this sample can provide a representative view of local perspectives on water reuse.

(e) Summary

The sampling approach focused on the local communities close to each demonstration site. The demographic characteristics of the respondents in Italy show no skew towards gender but do show a strong skew towards those between the ages of 19-58 with educational qualifications below the level of a university degree. These demographic and background differences must be considered before generalising findings from the present study.

5.02 Results from Social Acceptance (Italy)

This social acceptance survey was designed to inform the implementation of the Project Ô innovations across Europe and in Italy. Indeed, the primary focus of the survey was on attitudes towards the technology-based innovations for water treatment being implemented in respondents' local Project Ô demosite. To measure these attitudes, an explainer video of Project Ô's implementation of innovative water treatment technologies focusing on the project's innovation work in the respondents' country was produced.

(a) Presentation of the ADV.ERT Project Ô Technology Module

Respondents in Italy were presented with a pre-recorded video presentation⁴⁸ of the local Project Ô circular water economy solution, ADV.ERT, where it is being implemented (Puglia, Italy). The video presentation was designed to walk participants through the water sustainability innovation solution being deployed in the respondents' local Project Ô's demosite. In particular, the case of Italy, the video communicated the opportunity to increase water reuse with the ADV.ERT unit, and how this is beneficial for society, businesses and the environment.

Figure 54. ADV.ERT module video stills (Italy)

The presentation introduced and contextualised the general problem of contaminated groundwater resources, like aquifers. Being located too far away to rely on existing water treatment plants, some regions are forced to import

⁴⁸ Available at [Project Ô | ADV.ERT Module](#)

freshwater from other locations to meet local needs. The presentation explained how Project Ô's WTT is cleaning contaminated groundwater in a historic well in Puglia, Italy to restore this valuable resource.

The final section provided more technical information about the mobile Advanced Tertiary Treatment module called ADV.ERT. Finally, the video presentation concluded with an overview of benefits from this technology and how Project Ô innovations help to "close the loop" and ensure sustainable water use.

(b) Results of Social Acceptance of Technology

After the presentation, respondents were asked to mark a point on a Likert-type scale between pairs of opposing adjectives ('semantic differential') to indicate attitudes towards the technology and degree of social acceptance.

(i) Perceived Utility of ADV.ERT Technology MODULE

Respondents in Italy had generally positive attitudes towards the utility of the ADV.ERT technology solution (Figure 55)⁴⁹. Specifically, most respondents indicated that ADV.ERT was *Useful* (82%, n=162) compared to those who viewed it as *Useless* (8%, n=17). A similarly large proportion of respondents indicated that the ADV.ERT technology was *Valuable* (76%, n=156) rather than *Worthless* (10%, n=21), and *Essential* (82%, n=170) rather than *Unnecessary* (6%, n=13). Finally, most respondents viewed the ADV.ERT technology as more *Beneficial* (79%, n=161) than *Harmful* (9%, n=19).

⁴⁹ Useful-Useless (n=204, \bar{x} =1.99, SD=1.54)

Valuable-Worthless (n=205, \bar{x} =1.76, SD=1.64)

Essential-Unnecessary (n=207, \bar{x} =1.95, SD=1.41)

Beneficial-Harmful (n=205, \bar{x} =1.78, SD=1.59)

Figure 55. Perceived Utility of ADV.ERT Technology Module (Italy)

There was a clearly positive reception of the ADV.ERT solution from respondents in Italy. These results point to the primary areas where project efforts could reinforce social acceptance may be focused on the perceptions of utility, namely the benefits and value of the Project Ô technology.

(ii) Perceived Reliability & Safety of ADV.ERT Technology

Most respondents in Italy had positive views about the safety and reliability of the ADV.ERT module (Figure 56)⁵⁰. Indeed, respondents indicated views of the technology as *Reliable* (72%, n=150) rather than *Unreliable* (10%, n=23), and *Safe* (70%, n=145) compared to *Risky* (15%, n=32). However, compared to perceived utility, respondents were more undecided (as indicated by neutral responses) about the perceived reliability (n=32, 16%) and safety (n=29, 14%) of the ADV.ERT technology module. These views of the reliability and safety of ADV.ERT technology module in Italy are more positive than the assessments in Croatia ('Reliable': 72% ADV.ERT/Italy versus 64% PHOTO.CAT/Croatia. 'Safe': 70% ADV.ERT/Italy versus 60% PHOTO.CAT/Croatia).

Figure 56. Perceived Reliability & Safety of ADV.ERT Technology (Italy)

Respondent in Italy took a positive view of the ADV.ERT solution overall. At the same time, these results on social acceptance point to the room for further improvement in perceptions of the reliability and safety of the Project Ô technology.

⁵⁰ Safe-Risky (n=206, \bar{x} =1.36, SD=1.78)
 Reliable-Unreliable (n=205, \bar{x} =1.62, SD=1.62)

(iii) Qualitative results on social acceptance of Project Ô technology and solution implementation

This social acceptance survey research also included a qualitative, thought-listing dimension aimed at clarifying public views about the technical aspects of the Project Ô solution⁵¹. When describing the Project Ô water treatment technology being implemented at the local demosite, respondents in Italy often gave thoughts revolving around ‘sustainability’ ($n=21$) and ‘environment’ ($n=10$). This suggests that respondents view Project Ô technology as serving an environmental purpose. The Project Ô technology was also associated with ‘innovation’ ($n=9$), as well as being linked to some positive value judgments such as ‘interesting’ ($n=13$), ‘important’ ($n=11$), and ‘good’ ($n=10$).

Respondents’ thoughts about the ADV.ERT water treatment technology together show how the ‘sustainability’, ‘innovation’ and ‘interesting’ aspects are integrated in different ways. Some that appreciated the ‘sustainability’ aspect also pointed out its importance and suitability for Puglia specifically:

- *“It is a modern project, useful for environmental sustainability; Important; Technologically advanced; Suitable for Puglia; Useful for the planet”* (Man, age 39)
- *“Very important in the process of recovering contaminated water; Science; Work; Sustainability; Nature”* (Man, age 63)

Other responses focused more on the scientific process aspects of sustainability:

- *“Sustainability; water; Purification; Desalination; Transport”* (Woman, age 60)
- *“Israel risk desertification of biological filters; Biological filters; Desertification; Environmental risk; Bacteria”* (Man, age 68)

A focus on sustainability was also evident in responses that appreciated Project Ô’s ADV.ERT technology as innovative:

⁵¹ The survey question asked, ‘What comes to mind, if anything, when you think of the technology in the video you just watched?’ (referring to the video walk-through of the technology-based circular water economy solution introduced in the local demosite for the project.)

- *“Innovative, Sustainable, Indispensable; Useful; Innovative”* (Man, age 57)
- *“Sustainable; Economic; Innovative; For the environment; Green”* (Woman, age 33)
- *“Innovative’ Useful; Urgent; Sustainability; A lot”* (Man, age 35)

Some respondents also expressed personal interest in the Project Ô technology:

- *“It is an interesting technology; I hope it will be used very soon; It is a technology that approves of sustainability; I’m from Puglia and I really hope for this project in my region; Clean water for us and for our environment”* (Man, age 42)
- *“I am very interested in the purifier in question; Truly cutting-edge and interesting technology”* (Man, age 50)

The survey also asked about public views on the overall solution and its implementation at the local demosite⁵². The prominent themes in these qualitative responses focused on the Project Ô ‘technology’ ($n=27$) and its ‘innovative’ ($n=23$) nature. Digging deeper into the data, it is possible to delineate the ways in which different respondents thought about the ‘innovative’ ‘technology’ within the Project Ô implementation.

Some respondents’ thoughts around the technological approach of Project Ô implementation were linked to the ability to solve problems:

- *“Lack of clean water is becoming a major problem for the planet; Innovation; Technology; Groundwater; Purity”* (Man, age 22)
- *“Savings; Future; Pollution reduction; Solution of the problem; Technology”* (Man, age 48)

This sentiment around problem-solving and progression was also true for respondents that perceived the Project Ô solution as innovative:

- *“Innovative; Useful; Futuristic; Solution”* (Woman, 18)
- *“An innovative way not to throw the water away; Sustainability; Filtered; New; Enthusiastic”* (Man, age 39)
- *“Revolutionary; Innovative; Scientific; Confident; Technological”* (Man, age 19)

⁵² Respondents were given an opportunity to respond to the question ‘What comes to mind, if anything, when you think about the video you just watched?’ by typing up to 5 words in text boxes provided within the survey.

There was also a lasting sense of the Project Ô solution as ‘useful’ ($n=18$), ‘important’ ($n=11$) specifically for the purposes of sustainability:

- *“Important; sustainable; Useful for environmental sustainability”* (Woman, age 58)
- *“I plan to participate in this very important project; Improving the sustainability of water; I’d like to contribute to this project; seas would be cleaner thanks to project o; Clean water without pesticides”* (Man, age 42)
- *“A purifier is essential; Excellent investment; Innovation; Safe water great investment”* (Man, age 63)

Some respondents also expressed an appreciation of water itself as essential:

- *“That water is essential; Water is important for man”* (Man, age 17)
- *“That water is an essential good for humanity”* (Man, age 42)

Overall, respondents in Italy had similarly positive views about the technical aspects of the Project Ô solution and the overall implementation in the local demosite. These findings bode well for social acceptance of technology-based circular water economy solutions in Italy.

5.03 Results from Factors Relevant to Social Acceptance (Italy)

The survey measured key aspects of local views about local Project Ô innovation plans for water reuse, circular water economy and related issues. Here, we report findings from each survey question before identifying key patterns relevant to Project Ô's innovative water treatment technologies.

(a) Background views relevant to water reuse

To understand their background views relevant to water reuse, respondents were asked about their local water consumption experiences, their perceptions of the local water supply and their familiarity with water treatment technology. These data help to shed light on factors that may affect social acceptance of water reuse innovations.

(i) Personal Water Consumption

Respondents in Italy were asked to mark a point between always or never to indicate their personal water consumption and which drinking water sources⁵³ they used most often (Figure 57). Most respondents indicated their main source of drinking water was most often (always, usually or frequently) 'Water straight from the tap' (37%, n=74). This is far lower than the proportion of respondents in Croatia that drink water straight from the tap (37% Italy versus 88% Croatia), signally much less implicit trust in the local drinking water in Italy. The use of 'Filtered tap water' (36%, n=74) is also low among respondents in Italy, while use of 'Bottled water' (76%, n=161) is very high (compared to just 23% bottled water use for respondents in Croatia, for example).

⁵³ Response options included three categories for 'Water straight from the tap' (n=206, \bar{x} =3.61, SD=2.14), 'Filtered tap water' (n=205, \bar{x} =3.25, SD=2.39), and 'Bottled water' (n=209, \bar{x} =5.68, SD=1.68).

Always Usually Frequently Sometimes Occasionally Rarely Never

Figure 57. Familiarity with water treatment technology (Italy)

Likewise, many respondents in Italy indicated irregular (never or rarely) personal use of 'Filtered tap water' (52%, n=108) and 'Bottled water' (7%, n=15), and 'Water straight from the tap' (39%, n=81). These results show the primary source of drinking water for respondents in Italy was bottled water. Indeed, bottled water was used by a notable majority with some regularity, it was clearly the predominant water source within this sample. This is a noteworthy behavioural indicator, suggesting low confidence in the local supply of drinking water (motivating reliance on bottled water).

(ii) Community Water Supply Perceptions

Respondents were asked to mark a point on a Likert-type scale between pairs of opposing adjectives ('semantic differential') to indicate attitudes towards the community water supply in Italy.

Respondents had generally positive attitudes towards the practical importance of local water supply (Figure 58)⁵⁴. Indeed, most respondents indicated that the water supply was *Essential* (70%, n=143) compared to those who viewed it as *Unnecessary* (15%, n=30). A large proportion of respondents also indicated that the water supply was *Valuable* (71%, n=146) rather than *Worthless* (9%, n=20).

Figure 58. Perceived Utility of Community Water Supply (Italy)

Respondents in Italy had generally positive attitudes toward the safety and trustworthiness of the local water supply (Figure 59)⁵⁵. Specifically, most

⁵⁴ Essential-Unnecessary (n=204, \bar{x} =1.47, SD=1.77)

Valuable-Worthless (n=206, \bar{x} =1.50, SD=1.59)

⁵⁵ Safe-Risky (n=205, \bar{x} =0.90, SD=1.70)

Healthy-Unhealthy (n=207, \bar{x} =0.85, SD=1.76)

respondents indicated that the water supply was *Safe* (62%, n=127) compared to those who viewed it as *Risky* (20%, n=41). A large proportion of respondents also indicated that the water supply was *Healthy* (63%, n=130) rather than *Unhealthy* (21%, n=43). Finally, the majority of respondents viewed the water supply as more *Trustworthy* (61%, n=126) than *Untrustworthy* (21%, n=43).

Figure 59. Perceived Safety of Community Water Supply (Italy)

Respondents in Italy had generally positive attitudes towards the purity and naturalness of the local water supply (Figure 60)⁵⁶. Results show that most respondents indicated that their local water supply was *Natural* (62%, n=128) compared to those who viewed it as *Unnatural* (17%, n=34). A similarly large proportion of respondents indicated that the water supply was *Clean* (59%, n=122) rather than *Dirty* (22%, n=46), and *Pure* (55%, n=145) rather than *Impure* (24%, n=49).

Figure 60. Perceived Cleanliness of Community Water Supply (Italy)

Trustworthy-Untrustworthy (n=207, \bar{x} =0.88, SD=1.82)

⁵⁶ Nature-Unnatural (n=206, \bar{x} =1.06, SD=1.66)

Clean-Dirty (n=206, \bar{x} =0.83, SD=1.70)

Pure-Impure (n=204, \bar{x} =0.7, SD=1.74)

These results show respondents in Italy have broadly positive explicit views of community water supplies as natural, clean, and pure, despite their reported behaviour of relying on bottled water much more than tap water to drink. However, these results on social acceptance point to further project efforts that may bolster perceptions of how Project Ô technology can improve the community water supply sufficiently to reduce reliance on unsustainable bottled water for drinking.

(iii) Perceptions of Water Quality

To understand their background views relevant to water quality, respondents were asked about their perceptions of different categories⁵⁷ of local water supplies (Figure 61). Respondents indicated their views by marking a point on a Likert-type scale with anchors ranging from very good to very poor.

Most respondents in Italy view their water as good quality (very good or good). Indeed, the quality of *drinking water* (70%, n=141) was viewed in the most positive light compared to *surface water*⁵⁸ (46%, n=91) and *ground water*⁵⁹ (49%, n=96) water sources. These views on water quality are similar to Spain, and notably more negative than attitudes among respondents in Croatia (where drinking water, for example, received an 88% positive rating). Substantial levels of ‘neutral’ responses regarding surface and ground water suggest that fewer people have a clear sense of the quality of these water sources.

Figure 61. Water Quality Perceptions (Italy)

These survey results show general positive views of water quality in Italy (with the highest confidence indicated for drinking water). There is considerable

⁵⁷ Response options included three categories for ‘Drinking water’ (n=203, \bar{x} =3.79, SD=0.81), ‘Surface water’ (n=196, \bar{x} =3.23, SD=1.14), and ‘Ground water’ (n=199, \bar{x} =3.36, SD=1.08).

⁵⁸ Surface water was defined in the survey as including, ‘lakes, rivers, streams, creeks’.

⁵⁹ Ground water was defined in the survey as ‘e.g., water that is drawn from aquifers or wells’.

uncertainty about the status of surface and ground water supplies in Croatia, which should be considered in future social acceptance communication initiatives. It may be beneficial to highlight the value of Project Ô circular water management innovations for water quality in surface and ground sources in future public engagement.

(iv) Familiarity with Water Treatment Technology (WTT)

Respondents in Italy indicated their level of familiarity with water treatment technology (WTT) by marking a point on a Likert-type scale (Figure 62)⁶⁰. Most respondents were familiar with this type of technology to some extent (*slightly, somewhat or moderately familiar*; 84%, n=171). Much smaller proportions were either *extremely* (7%, n=14) or *not at all familiar* (10%, n=20) with this kind of technology.

Figure 62. Familiarity with water treatment technology (Italy)

These results show many of the respondents in Croatia have at least slight familiarity with WTT, with fairly few expressing complete unfamiliarity. This could be beneficial as a jumping off point for water treatment-related social acceptance campaigns in Italy.

(b) Perceptions of the Environment

To understand differences in perceptions about environmental factors, respondents in Italy were asked to mark a point on a Likert-type scale with anchors for *agree* or *disagree* to indicate their views. Each of the statements related to different aspects of environmental attitudes relevant to water treatment innovations. This is important for clarifying drivers of social acceptance of new water treatment solutions in Italy.

⁶⁰ Familiarity with WTT (n=205, \bar{x} =2.85, SD=1.08)

(i) Personal Perceptions of Relationship with the Environment

Respondents had generally positive perceptions of their relationship with the environment (Figure 63 and Figure 64)⁶¹. Most respondents agreed with the statement, *'My relationship to nature is an important part of who I am'* (84%, n=175), with relatively few disagreeing (4%, n=8). Similarly, the majority agreed with the statement, *'The environment is important to me'* (91%, n=189), and a much lower proportion disagreed (4%, n=9).

Figure 63. Personal Relationship with Environment (Italy)

These results were consistent for negatively framed attitude statements, where disagreement represents a positive relationship with the environment (Figure 64)⁶². Most respondents disagreed with the statement, *'There is nothing I can do personally to help protect the environment'* (81%, n=170), with a low proportion who agreed (12%, n=26). This is a similar environmental conservation self-efficacy attitude profile to respondents in Croatia. Likewise, the majority disagreed with the statement, *'I never talk about the environment with my family'* (68%, n=142). However, a much higher proportion agreed (22%, n=46) with this statement.

⁶¹ Relationship with Nature Identity (n=208, \bar{x} =5.66, SD=1.25)

Environment Importance (n=207, \bar{x} =6.08, SD=1.24)

⁶² Agency to Protect Environment (RC) (n=209, \bar{x} =2.29, SD=1.56)

Social Discuss Environment (RC) (n=209, \bar{x} =2.94, SD=1.85)

Figure 64. Personal Relationship with Environment (Reverse-coded) (Italy)

These results show broad recognition that the environment is an important part of respondents’ self-perception. Results also show a sense of self-efficacy regarding environmental protection. These are positive indicators for the project’s communication efforts, suggesting that an environmental sustainability focus in social acceptance messaging may find a ready audience in Italy. However, results show that positive environmental views within this pool of respondents are less commonly shared with others through discussion. This may point to the need for other additional framing options (e.g., economic benefits) in community engagement efforts.

(ii) General Perceptions of the Environment

Respondents also viewed protecting the environment as a priority (Figure 65)⁶³. Most respondents agreed with the controversial statement, *‘Keeping lakes and rivers clean is more important than protecting people’s jobs’* (58%, n=117), with a lower proportion who disagreed (14%, n=29) and remained neutral (27%, n=55).

Figure 65. General Perceptions of Environment (Italy)

However, these results were less consistent with a negatively framed attitude statement (where disagreement represents prioritising the environment) that juxtaposes economic and environmental priorities (Figure 66)⁶⁴. Specifically, while a larger proportion of respondents disagreed with the controversial statement, *‘Protecting people’s jobs is more important than the*

⁶³ Importance of protecting jobs compared to rivers and lakes (n=201, \bar{x} =4.96, SD=1.59)

⁶⁴ Importance of protecting jobs compared to environment (RC) (n=205, \bar{x} =4.03, SD=1.76)

environment' (37%, n=76), the proportions were still high for those who agreed (33%, n=68) and remained neutral (30%, n=61).

Figure 66. General Perceptions of the Environment (Reverse-coded) (Italy)

Finally, respondents had mixed views about the capacity of modern science to resolve environmental issues (Figure 67)⁶⁵. Similarly, results for those who disagreed with the controversial statement, '*Modern science will solve our environmental problems*' (23%, n=47) were more equally divided between those who agreed (54%, n=110) and remained neutral (23%, n=48). These views from respondents in Italy were comparatively positive about the power of science to address problems in the natural environment: For example, among respondents in Croatia only 36% agreed with this statement, while 43% disagreed.

Figure 67. General Perceptions of the Environment (Reverse-coded) (Italy)

These results suggest that while respondents in Italy tended to view the environment as important, there was ambivalence about prioritising environmental sustainability over important non-environmental factors. Thus, project communications should extend beyond environmental sustainability framing by also emphasising economic and other benefits associated with a shift to a circular economy model. This multi-faceted messaging approach may be effective at developing greater social acceptance of the project's circular water management solutions in Italy, given the findings presented here.

⁶⁵ Modern science capacity to resolve environmental issues (RC) (n=205, \bar{x} =4.48, SD=1.49)

(c) Trust in Science and the European Commission

To understand the role of trust towards science and technology, scientists and engineers and the European Commission in social acceptance of Project Ô innovation work, respondents in Croatia were asked to mark a point on a Likert-type scale with anchors for completely trust to completely distrust to indicate their views.

(i) Trust in Science & Technology

Respondents in Italy were asked about their trust in general towards science and technology (Figure 68)⁶⁶. Most respondents indicated high levels of trust (partial or complete) in 'science' (84%, n=173) and 'technology' (82%, n=169). There were only small differences between trust in science and trust in technology ($\pm 2\%$). Similar to Spain, these results are particularly positive in comparison with other demosite regions such as Croatia (Croatia: 'Science' 72% trust and 'Technology' 67% trust).

Figure 68. General Trust in Science & Technology (Italy)

Trust towards science and technology was overwhelmingly positive. A minority of respondents indicated some level of distrust (partial or complete) in both 'science' (4%, n=8) and 'technology' (6%, n=12), although complete distrust was exceedingly rare.

(ii) Trust in Scientists & Engineers

Respondents in Italy were asked about their levels of trust in specific categories of professionals relevant to Project Ô, namely scientists and

⁶⁶ Trust in Science (n=205, \bar{x} =1.39, SD=0.88)
Trust in Technology (n=207, \bar{x} =1.11, SD=0.94)

engineers (Figure 69)⁶⁷. Most respondents indicated high levels of trust (partial or complete) in ‘scientists’ (82%, n=168) and ‘engineers’ (66%, n=134), with small differences between the two categories ($\pm 16\%$). These levels of trust in scientists and engineers are comparatively high: For example, a smaller proportion of respondents in Croatia expressed trust in scientists (65%) and engineers (70%).

Figure 69. General Trust in Scientists & Engineers (Italy)

While the results in Italy show similarly high levels of trust for both scientists and engineers, it is worth acknowledging there is some distrust in these professions amongst a minority of respondents (*partial* or *complete*) in both ‘scientists’ (7%, n=14) and ‘engineers’ (8%, n=17). It is also noteworthy that engineers gained a slightly higher level of trust compared to scientists.

(iii) Trust in The European Commission

Respondents in Croatia were asked about their general level of trust in the European Commission (EC) (Figure 70)⁶⁸. Respondents indicated mixed views, with a higher level of distrust (26%, n=54) compared to trust (45%, n=91) in the EC. This is a relatively low level of distrust when compared to other demosite regions, such as Croatia, where we found 40% expressing distrust in the EC on this question (and only 29% expressing trust in the EC). It is also noteworthy that a sizable proportion of respondents indicated neutral views (29%, n=59), which may indicate a lack of strong pre-existing perspectives on this topic.

⁶⁷ Trust in Scientists (n=206, \bar{x} =1.21, SD=0.96)

Trust in Engineers (n=202, \bar{x} =0.85, SD=1.01)

⁶⁸ Trust in European Commission (n=204, \bar{x} = 0.15, SD=1.19)

Figure 70. General Trust in European Commission (Italy)

This social acceptance survey extended questions about the EC to gather deeper, more project-relevant insights from respondents in Italy. This is important because the project is explicitly presented as an investment by the EC aimed at improving lives in Europe. Specifically, two additional questions were asked about the relationship between the EC and the respondents' local community (Figure 71 and Figure 72). For these questions, respondents were asked to mark a point on a Likert-type scale with anchors ranging from *strongly agree* to *strongly disagree* to indicate their views.

Respondents had mixed levels of trust that EC actions would be appropriate (or aligned) for their community (Figure 71)⁶⁹. More respondents disagreed with the statement, '*I trust the European Commission to do what is right for my community*' (23%, n=47) compared to those who agreed (46%, n=95) or indicated neutral (31%, n=68) views. These are notably favourable levels of trust in the EC to do the right thing for their community compared to what we found in some other demosite regions, such as Croatia, where 42% of respondents disagreed with this statement and only 25% agreed.

Figure 71. Trust in EC - Align Actions for Community (Italy)

These results were consistent with the next question, which was a negatively framed attitude statement (where disagreement represents positive views) that juxtaposes EC and community support. Indeed, respondents had mixed levels of confidence about the ability of the EC to help their community (Figure 72)⁷⁰. Fewer respondents disagreed with the statement, '*I have very little confidence in the European Commission's ability to help my community*' (23%,

⁶⁹ Trust in European Commission Actions Appropriate for Community (n=207, \bar{x} = 3.24, SD=1.13)

⁷⁰ Confidence in European Commission Ability to Help Community (n=207, \bar{x} = 3.27, SD=1.09)

n=47), compared to those who agreed (46%, n=95) or indicated neutral (31%, n=65) views.

Figure 72. Confidence in EC Ability to Help Community (Reverse-coded) (Italy)

These results suggest that there is substantial distrust in the European Commission among respondents in Italy. This represents a major challenge to social acceptance of the project implementation and outcomes in Italy.

5.04 Discussion (Italy)

As in other demosite regions, this social acceptance research in Italy was designed to inform the implementation of Project Ô circular water management solutions. Sampling centred on communities close to the local demonstration site. While the demographic characteristics for respondents in Italy show no gender skew, there was a strong skew in education level towards those with education below university degree level, and people between the ages of 19-58. These demographic profile details help to clarify the coverage of the sample.

There was widespread recognition of WTT among Italy-based respondents, with 'complete unfamiliarity' being relatively rare. This starting awareness of water treatment innovations could benefit campaigns to increase social acceptance in Italy. Respondents' local water consumption habits further clarify factors affecting social acceptance of circular water management solutions. The primary source of drinking water for respondents in Italy was bottled water. Indeed, bottled water was used by a notable majority with some regularity, it was clearly the predominant water source within this sample. This is an important behavioural indicator of *low confidence* in the local drinking water supply. Conversely, directly measured, respondents in Italy presented generally positive views of water quality, with high confidence in drinking water (comparable to Croatia and Spain).

While the environment is an important part of how respondents in Italy perceive themselves, some respondents were less inclined to prioritise environmental sustainability over important non-environmental factors. Furthermore, views about the environment were less commonly shared with others through discussion.

Respondents in Italy show levels of trust in the European Commission that were similar to Spain but higher than Croatia. One possible explanation could be perceptions of the EC as closer or more accessible to their community. Regardless, the evident distrust may represent a challenge to social acceptance of the project implementation and outcomes in Italy because the project is explicitly presented as an EC investment aimed at improving lives in Europe.

Section VI. Israel Social Acceptance Case Study

6.01 Survey Sampling (Israel)

The sampling approach focused on the regions close to each demonstration site. This section sets out the demographic characteristics of the respondents to the survey in Israel that focused on the region around Eilat (n=204 achieved sample).

(a) Gender

Respondents in the Israel survey self-reported their gender identification (Figure 73). There was a higher proportion of men (71%, n=142) compared to women (29%, n=57). No respondents self-identified as non-binary.

Figure 73. Gender distribution of respondents (Israel)

(b) Age Profile

Young respondents were over-represented in the Israel sample (Figure 74). The age categories with the largest proportions were 19-28 years (40%, n=82), 29-38 years (26%, n=52) and 39-48 years (13%, n=27), followed by 49-58 years (8%, n=16). Whereas, much smaller proportions were between ages of 59-68 years (5%, n=11), ≤18 years (6%, n=13), and ≥68 years (1%, n=2).

Figure 74. Age bands for survey respondents (Israel)

The mean age of respondents was 33 and the median was 30. This distribution indicates a clear skew toward younger and middle-aged respondents, particularly those between 18-38 in the Israel sample.

(c) Education

The educational qualification profile of respondents in the Israel survey over-represented those with university degrees and above (57% vs. 43%) (Figure 75). Indeed, the educational qualification response category with the highest proportion was 'University degree' (42%, n=82). The response categories with the next highest proportion were 'Below university degree' (35%, n=69) followed by 'Postgraduate degree' (15%, n=29). The response category with the lowest representation was 'No educational qualification' (8%, n=15).

Figure 75. Educational qualifications of respondents (Israel)

(d) Connections to Water Treatment Research or Industry

Respondents in Israel were asked about any prior employment (Figure 76), and knowledge of others employed (Figure 77), in water treatment or hydrology fields. Most respondents had no prior water industry/research-related employment (70%, n=140) and most did not personally know anyone who was employed (62%, n=123) in these related fields.

Figure 76. Responses to 'Previous employment' in water treatment (Israel)

Figure 77. Responses to 'Relation to others employed' in water treatment (Israel)

These results show that the sample in Israel did not have an excessive number of water-related research or industry participants. This helps give reassurance that this sample can provide a representative view of local perspectives on water reuse.

(e) Summary

The sampling approach focused on the local communities close to each demonstration site. The respondent profile in Israel over-represents men between the ages of 19-38 with educational qualifications above the university degree level. Such demographic patterns must be considered before generalising findings from the present study.

6.02 Results from Social Acceptance Study (Israel)

This social acceptance survey was designed to inform the implementation of the Project Ô innovations across Europe and in Israel. Indeed, the primary focus of the survey was on attitudes towards the technology-based innovations for water treatment being implemented in respondents' local Project Ô demosite. To measure these attitudes, an explainer video of Project Ô's implementation of innovative water treatment technologies focusing on the project's innovation work in the respondents' country was produced.

(a) Presentation of Project Ô technology-solutions

Respondents in Israel were presented with a video-recorded account⁷¹ focusing on the local Project Ô water treatment technology module, SALTECH, (demosite in Eilat, Israel). The video presented the circular water management solution being implemented in respondents' local Project Ô's demosite. This video noted the opportunity to increase water reuse with the SALTECH unit, and articulated why this is beneficial for society, businesses and the environment.

Figure 78. SALTECH module video stills (Israel)

The presentation introduced and contextualised the general problem of

⁷¹ Available at [Project Ô | SALTECH Module](#)

the negative environmental impacts of wastewater from fish farming systems. The presentation explained how Project Ô WTT enables water to be reused sustainably in fish farming systems. The final section provided more technical information about the SALTECH module, the WTT installed at the National Centre for Mariculture in Israel to treat wastewater from land-based fish farms.

Finally, the video presentation concluded with an overview of benefits from this technology and how Project Ô innovations help to “close the loop” and ensure sustainable water use.

(b) Results of Social Acceptance of Technology

After the presentation, respondents were asked to mark a point on a Likert-type scale between pairs of opposing adjectives (‘semantic differential’) to indicate attitudes towards the technology and degree of social acceptance.

(i) Perceived Utility of SALTECH Technology

Respondents in Israel had generally positive attitudes towards the utility of the SALTECH technology solution (Figure 79)⁷². Specifically, most respondents indicated that the technology module was Useful (75%, n=152) compared to those who viewed it as Useless (15%, n=32). A similarly large proportion of respondents indicated that the technology was Valuable (66%, n=134) rather than Worthless (18%, n=37), and Essential (67%, n=136) rather than Unnecessary (18%, n=38). Finally, most respondents viewed the technology module as more Beneficial (72%, n=148) than Harmful (16%, n=34).

⁷² Useful-Useless (n=204, \bar{x} =1.48, SD=1.79)

Valuable-Worthless (n=204, \bar{x} =1.21, SD=1.76)

Essential-Unnecessary (n=204, \bar{x} =1.29, SD=1.74)

Beneficial-Harmful (n=204, \bar{x} =1.37, SD=1.74)

Figure 79. Perceived Utility of SALTECH Technology (Israel)

These results show a broadly positive reception of SALTECH solution from respondents in Israel. Additional communication initiative aimed at reinforcing social acceptance could focus on addressing perceptions of utility, namely the benefits and value of the Project Ô technology.

(ii) Perceived Reliability & Safety of SALTECH Technology

Positive attitudes towards the safety and reliability of the SALTECH technology module predominated in the Israel sample (Figure 80)⁷³. Indeed, the SALTECH technology module was viewed as Reliable (64%, n=131) rather than Unreliable (17%, n=35), and Safe (65%, n=133) compared to Risky (20%, n=41). However, compared to perceived utility, respondents were more undecided (as indicated by neutral responses) about the perceived reliability (n=39,19%) and safety (n=38,19%) of the SALTECH technology module.

Figure 80. Perceived Reliability & Safety of SALTECH Technology (Israel)

These empirical results clearly show a positive reception of the SALTECH solution from respondents in Israel. However, these social acceptance findings highlight where further project efforts to improve perceptions of reliability and safety of the Project Ô technology could best be targeted.

⁷³ Safe-Risky (n=204, \bar{x} =1.04, SD=1.72)

Reliable-Unreliable (n=204, \bar{x} =1.10, SD=1.79)

(iii) Qualitative results on social acceptance of Project Ô technology and solution implementation

This social acceptance survey research also included a qualitative, thought-listing dimension aimed at clarifying public views about the *technology* aspects of the Project Ô solution⁷⁴. Common themes that arose included a view of the technology as ‘good’ ($n=20$) or ‘great’ ($n=7$), as well as ‘important’ ($n=11$). Digging deeper into this data, it is possible to gain more insight into how these ‘good’ and ‘important’ aspects were integrated into broader thought patterns about Project Ô implementation.

When describing the Project Ô water treatment technology being implemented at the local demosite, respondents expressed a perception of it as ‘good’ both in terms of the concept, the impacts for their community, in terms of the technology itself:

- *“Interesting; Good for us”* (Woman, age 38)
- *“Good technology”* (Woman, age 42)
- *“Good thoughts”* (Man, age 18)

Respondents highlighted different aspects of importance of the technology, including the water it interacts with and the benefits it could provide to humans:

- *“Great idea; It is important; Caring; Professional thinking; Good for the world”* (Woman, age 30)
- *“Owes to advanced technology; Important; Important for health”* (Woman, age 53)
- *“That water is very important”* (Woman, age 40)

The survey also asked about public views on the overall solution and its implementation at the local demosite⁷⁵. Respondents in Israel frequently expressed positive value-based perceptions of the solution, including that they found it ‘interesting’ ($n=22$), ‘good’ ($n=18$), and ‘stunning’ ($n=9$). Other prominent themes within responses to this question included the ‘environment’ ($n=10$) and it being ‘important’ ($n=12$).

⁷⁴ The survey question asked, ‘What comes to mind, if anything, when you think of the technology in the video you just watched?’ (referring to the video walk-through of the technology-based circular water economy solution introduced in the local demosite)

⁷⁵ Respondents were given an opportunity to respond to the question ‘What comes to mind, if anything, when you think about the video you just watched?’ by typing up to 5 words in text boxes provided within the survey.

Responses about the water treatment technology shows that how 'interesting', 'environment' and 'importance' were integrated into thoughts about Project Ô technology. Those that expressed interest did highlighted the role of science and newness of the technology:

- *"Interesting; Amazing science; Stunning"* (Man, age 36)
- *"New technology; Interesting"* (Man, age 45)

Others specifically focused on their interest in the concept of Project Ô as a solution:

- *"Interesting thoughts"* (Woman, age 20)
- *"Interesting idea"* (Man, age 38)

Several responses highlighted specific aspects of the environment that they perceived the solution as related to:

- *"Environment protection; Pure water; Fisheries; Sea water; Technology"* (Man, age 28)
- *"Risk in the water system; Contaminated with water; Importance of protecting the environment; Preserve nature; Help & contribute to the environment as much as possible"* (Woman, age 34)
- *"Conservation of water in the environment & nature"* (Man, age 27)

Respondents that expressed a perception of the project as important did so in the context of the water it interacts with being important, as well as the importance of the environment and technology's role in improving environmental and human outcomes:

- *"It is very important to think about the environment and you should already take good steps"* (Man, age 30)
- *"How important is technology in the field of water"* (Man, age 28)
- *"Water is important"* (Man, age 50)
- *"We are on our way to an important step towards a healthy life"* (Woman, age 28)

Overall, respondents in Israel had similarly positive views about the technology aspects of the Project Ô solution and the overall implementation in the local demosite. These findings bode well for social acceptance of technology-based circular water economy solutions in Israel.

6.03 Results from Factors Relevant to Social Acceptance (Israel)

The survey measured key aspects of local views about local Project Ô innovation plans for water reuse, circular water economy and related issues. Here, we report findings from each survey question before identifying key patterns relevant to Project Ô's innovative water treatment technologies.

(a) Background views relevant to water reuse

To understand their background views relevant to water reuse, respondents were asked about their water consumption behaviours, their perceptions of the local water supply and their familiarity with water treatment technology. These data help to shed light on factors that may affect social acceptance of water reuse innovations.

(i) Personal Water Consumption

Respondents in Israel were asked to mark a point between always or never to indicate their personal water consumption and which drinking water sources⁷⁶ they used most often (Figure 81). Most respondents indicated their main source of drinking water was most often (always, usually or frequently) 'Water straight from the tap' (36%, n=74), compared to 'Filtered tap water' (56%, n=113) and 'Bottled water' (61%, n=123). This is a high level of bottled water use and low level of tap water usage, as we found with respondents in Italy.

Figure 81. Water Sources for Personal Consumption (Israel)

⁷⁶ Response options included three categories for 'Water straight from the tap' (n=204, \bar{x} =3.88, SD=1.97), 'Filtered tap water' (n=202, \bar{x} =4.56, SD=2.11), and 'Bottled water' (n=203, \bar{x} =4.81, SD=1.78).

Likewise, many respondents indicated irregular (never or rarely) personal use of 'Filtered tap water' (23%, n=47) and 'Bottled water' (14%, n=30), and 'Water straight from the tap' (34%, n=69). These results show the primary sources of drinking water for respondents in Israel was bottled or filtered. Indeed, bottled water was used by a notable majority with some regularity, it was clearly the predominant water source within this sample. This is a noteworthy behavioural indicator of confidence in the local supply of drinking water.

(ii) Community Water Supply Perceptions

Respondents were asked to mark a point on a Likert-type scale between pairs of opposing adjectives ('semantic differential') to indicate attitudes towards the community water supply in Israel.

Respondents had generally positive attitudes towards the practical importance of local water supply (Figure 82)⁷⁷. Indeed, most respondents indicated that the water supply was Essential (56%, n=114) compared to those who viewed it as Unnecessary (24%, n=48). A large proportion of respondents also indicated that the water supply was Valuable (62%, n=126) rather than Worthless (20%, n=41). While skewing positive, these figures are relatively low compared to what we found in Croatia, for example (Croatia: 77% 'Essential' and 75% 'Valuable').

Figure 82. Perceived Utility of Community Water Supply (Israel)

Respondents in Israel had generally positive attitudes toward the safety and trustworthiness of the local water supply (Figure 83)⁷⁸. Specifically, most respondents indicated that the water supply was Safe (54%, n=112) compared

⁷⁷ Essential-Unnecessary (n=204, \bar{x} =0.97, SD=1.92)

Valuable-Worthless (n=203, \bar{x} =1.03, SD=1.75)

⁷⁸ Safe-Risky (n=204, \bar{x} =0.78, SD=1.92)

Healthy-Unhealthy (n=202, \bar{x} =0.89, SD=1.83)

Trustworthy-Untrustworthy (n=203, \bar{x} =0.67, SD=1.88)

to those who viewed it as Risky (25%, n=52). A large proportion of respondents also indicated that the water supply was Healthy (58%, n=118) rather than Unhealthy (23%, n=47). While skewing positive, these results are more negative than what we found in Croatia, for example (Croatia: 72% 'Healthy'). Finally, most respondents viewed the water supply as more Trustworthy (52%, n=106) than Untrustworthy (27%, n=55). These results from respondents in Israel are also notably less positive than our findings in Croatia (Croatia: 64% 'Trustworthy').

Figure 83. Perceived Safety of Community Water Supply (Israel)

Respondents in Israel had generally positive attitudes towards the purity and naturalness of the water supply (Figure 84)⁷⁹. Results show that most respondents indicated that the water supply was Natural (53%, n=106) compared to those who viewed it as Unnatural (29%, n=60). A similarly large proportion of respondents indicated that the water supply was Clean (58%, n=118) rather than Dirty (25%, n=51) and Pure (54%, n=110) rather than Impure (26%, n=53). These survey results from Israel are all less positive than the views expressed by respondents in Croatia (Croatia: 76% 'Natural', 71% 'Clean' and 77% 'Pure').

⁷⁹ Nature-Unnatural (n=203, \bar{x} =0.64, SD=1.82)
 Clean-Dirty (n=203, \bar{x} =0.90, SD=1.82)
 Pure-Impure (n=203, \bar{x} =0.63, SD=1.76)

Figure 84. Perceived Cleanliness of Community Water Supply (Israel)

These results show respondents in Israel have broadly positive views of community water supplies as natural, clean, and pure. However, these results on social acceptance point to further project efforts that may bolster perceptions of how Project Ô technology can improve the community water supply.

(iii) Perceptions of Water Quality

To understand their background views relevant to water quality, respondents were asked about their perceptions of different categories⁸⁰ of local water supplies (Figure 85). Respondents indicated their views by marking a point on a Likert-type scale with anchors ranging from very good to very poor.

Most respondents in Israel view their water as good quality (very good or good). Indeed, the quality of drinking water (70%, n=140) was viewed in the most positive light compared to surface water⁸¹ (50%, n=96) and ground water⁸² (56%, n=104) water sources. Substantial levels of 'neutral' responses regarding surface and ground water suggest that fewer people have a clear sense of the quality of these water sources.

Figure 85. Water Quality Perceptions (Israel)

These results show general positive views of water quality in Israel, with the highest confidence placed in drinking water. There is considerable uncertainty about the status of surface and ground water supplies in Israel, which should be considered in future social acceptance communication initiatives. It may be beneficial to highlight the benefits of Project Ô circular

⁸⁰ Response options included three categories for 'Drinking water' (n=199, \bar{x} =3.87, SD=1.06), 'Surface water' (n=194, \bar{x} =3.38, SD=1.09), and 'Ground water' (n=194, \bar{x} =3.50, SD=1.15).

⁸¹ Surface water was defined in the survey as including, 'lakes, rivers, streams, creeks'.

⁸² Ground water was defined in the survey as 'e.g., water that is drawn from aquifers or wells'.

water economy innovations for water quality in surface and ground sources in future public engagement.

(iv) Familiarity With Water Treatment Technology

Respondents in Israel indicated their level of familiarity with water treatment technology (WTT) by marking a point on a Likert-type scale (Figure 86)⁸³. The majority of respondents were familiar with this type of technology to some extent (slightly, somewhat or moderately familiar; 74%, n=146). Much smaller proportions were either extremely (8%, n=16) or not at all familiar (19%, n=37) with this kind of technology.

Figure 86. Familiarity with water treatment technology (Israel)

These results show broad recognition of WTT among Israel-based respondents, with a small minority expressing complete unfamiliarity. This suggests that there is a base of existing awareness of water treatment innovations to draw upon when seeking social acceptance for related innovations in Israel.

(b) Perceptions of the Environment

To understand differences in perceptions about environmental factors, respondents in Israel were asked to mark a point on a Likert-type scale with anchors for agree or disagree to indicate their views. Each of the statements related to different aspects of environmental attitudes relevant to water treatment innovations. This is important for clarifying drivers of social acceptance of new water treatment solutions in Israel.

⁸³ Familiarity with WTT (n=199, \bar{x} =2.72, SD=1.21)

(i) Personal Perceptions of Relationship with Environment

Respondents had generally positive perceptions of their relationship with the environment (Figure 87 and Figure 88)⁸⁴. Most respondents agreed with the statement, *'My relationship to nature is an important part of who I am'* (62%, n=124), with relatively few disagreeing (20%, n=37). Similarly, the majority agreed with the statement, *'The environment is important to me'* (80%, n=156), and a much lower proportion disagreed (10%, n=19).

Figure 87. Personal Relationship with Environment (Israel)

These results were consistent for negatively framed attitude statements, where disagreement represents a positive relationship with the environment (Figure 88)⁸⁵. Most respondents disagreed with the statement, *'There is nothing I can do personally to help protect the environment'* (62%, n=124), with a low proportion who agreed (22%, n=44). Likewise, the majority disagreed with the statement, *'I never talk about the environment with my family'* (52%).

Figure 88. Personal Relationship with Environment (Reverse-coded) (Israel)

These results show that the natural environment is important to many respondents in Israel. Results also show a sense of self-efficacy regarding

⁸⁴ Relationship with Nature Identity (n=198, \bar{x} =4.93, SD=1.63)
Environment Importance (n=196, \bar{x} =5.65, SD=1.45)

⁸⁵ Agency to Protect Environment (RC) (n=197, \bar{x} =3.06, SD=1.79)
Social Discuss Environment (RC) (n=198, \bar{x} =3.54, SD=1.85)

environmental protection. These are positive indicators for the project's communication efforts, suggesting that an environmental sustainability focus in social acceptance messaging may find a ready audience in Israel. However, results show that positive environmental views within this pool of respondents are less commonly shared with others through discussion. This may point to the need for other additional framing options (e.g., economic benefits) in community engagement efforts.

(ii) General Perceptions of the Environment

Respondents also viewed protecting the environment as a priority (Figure 89)⁸⁶. Most respondents agreed with the controversial statement, *'Keeping lakes and rivers clean is more important than protecting people's jobs'* (59%, n=118), with a lower proportion who disagreed (21%, n=42) and remained neutral (18%, n=36).

Figure 89. General Perceptions of Environment (Israel)

However, these results were less consistent with a negatively framed attitude statement (where disagreement represents prioritising the environment) that juxtaposes economic and environmental priorities (Figure 90)⁸⁷. Specifically, while a larger proportion of respondents disagreed with the controversial statement, *'Protecting people's jobs is more important than the environment'* (40%, n=78), the proportions were still high for those who agreed (36%, n=71) and remained neutral (24%, n=48).

⁸⁶ Importance of protecting jobs compared to rivers and lakes (n=196, \bar{x} =4.8, SD=1.70)

⁸⁷ Importance of protecting jobs compared to environment (RC) (n=197, \bar{x} =3.97, SD=1.72)

Figure 90. General Perceptions of the Environment (Reverse-coded) (Israel)

Finally, respondents had mixed views about the capacity of modern science to resolve environmental issues (Figure 91)⁸⁸. Similarly, results for those who disagreed with the controversial statement, *'Modern science will solve our environmental problems'* (54%, n=105) were more equally divided between those who agreed (24%, n=47) and remained neutral (22%, n=42).

Figure 91. General Perceptions of the Environment (Reverse-coded) (Israel)

These results suggests that while the environment is an important part of how respondents perceive themselves, some respondents may be less inclined to prioritise environmental sustainability over important non-environmental factors. Thus, project communications should extend beyond environmental sustainability framing by also emphasising economic and other benefits associated with a shift to a circular economy model. This multi-faceted messaging approach may be effective at developing social acceptance in Israel, given the findings presented here.

⁸⁸ Modern science capacity to resolve environmental issues (RC) (n=194, \bar{x} =4.48, SD=1.56)

(c) Trust in Science and the European Commission

To understand the role of trust towards science and technology, scientists and engineers and the European Commission in social acceptance of Project Ô innovation work, respondents in Israel were asked to mark a point on a Likert-type scale with anchors for completely trust to completely distrust to indicate their views.

(i) Trust in Science & Technology

Respondents in Israel were asked about their trust in general towards science and technology (Figure 92)⁸⁹. Most respondents indicated high levels of trust (partial or complete) in 'science' (74%, n=147) and 'technology' (67%, n=137). There were only small differences between trust in science and trust in technology ($\pm 7\%$).

Figure 92. General Trust in Science & Technology (Israel)

Trust towards science and technology was overwhelmingly positive. A minority of respondents indicated some level of distrust (partial or complete) in both 'science' (11%, n=21) and 'technology' (14%, n=28), although completely distrust was exceedingly rare.

(ii) Trust in Scientists & Engineers

Respondents in Israel were asked about their levels of trust in specific categories of professionals relevant to Project Ô, namely scientists and engineers (Figure 93)⁹⁰. Most respondents indicated high levels of trust (partial

⁸⁹ Trust in Science (n=198, \bar{x} =0.98, SD=1.07)

Trust in Technology (n=197, \bar{x} =0.82, SD=1.13)

⁹⁰ Trust in Scientists (n=197, \bar{x} =0.91, SD=1.05)

Trust in Engineers (n=196, \bar{x} =0.83, SD=1.05)

or complete) in ‘scientists’ (72%, n=141) and ‘engineers’ (69%, n=136), with small differences between the two categories ($\pm 3\%$).

Figure 93. General Trust in Scientists & Engineers (Israel)

While these results show similarly high levels of trust for both scientists and engineers, it is worth noting there is some distrust in these professions amongst a minority of respondents (partial or complete) in both ‘scientists’ (10%, n=20) and ‘engineers’ (13%, n=25). It is also noteworthy that engineers gained a slightly higher level of trust compared to scientists.

(iii) Trust in The European Commission

Respondents in Israel were asked about their general level of trust in the European Commission (EC) (Figure 94)⁹¹. Respondents indicated mixed views, with a higher level of distrust (36%, n=68) compared to trust (32%, n=60) in the EC. It is also noteworthy that a sizable proportion of respondents indicated neutral views (32%, n=59), which may indicate a lack of strong pre-existing perspectives on this topic.

Figure 94. General Trust in European Commission (Israel)

This social acceptance survey extended questions about the EC to gather deeper, more project-relevant insights from respondents in Israel. This is important because the project is explicitly presented as an investment by the EC aimed at improving lives in Europe. Specifically, two additional questions were asked about the relationship between the EC and the respondents’ local

⁹¹ Trust in European Commission (n=187, \bar{x} = -0.12, SD=1.17)

community (Figure 95 and Figure 96). For these questions, respondents were asked to mark a point on a Likert-type scale with anchors ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree to indicate their views.

Respondents had mixed levels of trust that EC actions would be appropriate (or aligned) for their community (Figure 95)⁹². More respondents disagreed with the statement, '*I trust the European Commission to do what is right for my community*' (28%, n=72) compared to those who agreed (38%, n=72) or indicated neutral (34%, n=65) views.

Figure 95. Trust in EC - Align Actions for Community (Israel)

These results were consistent with the next question, which was a negatively framed attitude statement (where disagreement represents positive views) that juxtaposes EC and community support. Indeed, respondents had mixed levels of confidence about the ability of the EC to help their community (Figure 96)⁹³. Fewer respondents disagreed with the statement, '*I have very little confidence in the European Commission's ability to help my community*' (23%, n=43), compared to those who agreed (41%, n=77) or indicated neutral (36%, n=68) views.

Figure 96. Confidence in EC Ability to Help Community (Reverse-coded item) (Israel)

These results suggest that there is substantial distrust in the European Commission among respondents in Israel. There are also many who simply have no opinion. This represents a major challenge to social acceptance of the project implementation and outcomes in Israel.

⁹² Trust in European Commission Actions Appropriate for Community (n=192, \bar{x} = 3.79, SD=1.11)

⁹³ Confidence in European Commission Ability to Help Community (n=188, \bar{x} = 3.22, SD=1.08)

6.04 Discussion (Israel)

This social acceptance research was designed to inform the implementation of the Project Ó innovations in Israel. The sampling approach focused on the local communities close to each demonstration site. The profile of respondents in Israel was, however, found to skew towards men aged 19-38 with university educations. There was widespread familiarity with WTT among Israel-based respondents, with a relatively small minority expressing complete unfamiliarity. These findings indicate a pool of existing interest in and familiarity with water treatment innovations that could be an asset to the project's efforts to develop social acceptance in Israel.

Respondents' water consumption patterns are also relevant to social acceptance of circular water management innovations. The primary source of drinking water for respondents in Israel was bottled water. Indeed, bottled water was used by a notable majority with some regularity, it was clearly the predominant water source within this sample. This is an important implicit behavioural indicator of *low confidence* in the local drinking water supply. However, when explicitly measured, respondents in Israel presented generally positive views of water quality, with high confidence in drinking water (comparable level to Croatia and Spain).

While the environment is an important part of how respondents in Israel perceive themselves, some respondents were less inclined to prioritise environmental sustainability over important non-environmental factors. Furthermore, views about the environment were less commonly shared with others through discussion.

Respondents in Israel show levels of trust in the European Commission that substantially lower than Spain and Italy. One possible explanation for why this trust faltered for respondents in Israel could be perceptions of the EC as distant or inaccessible from their community. One possible explanation could be perceptions of the EC as closer or more accessible to their community. Regardless, the evident distrust may represent a challenge to social acceptance of the project

implementation and outcomes in Italy because the project is explicitly presented as an EC investment aimed at improving lives in Europe.

